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SURGICAL FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH UNPLANNED INTUBATIONS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Currently, there is limited data addressing surgical factors that contribute to unplanned intubations (UIs). The American College of Surgeons (ACS) National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) defines UIs as a circumstance that requires the unanticipated placement of an endotracheal tube or similar device, such as the laryngeal mask airway (LMA) or nasotracheal tube with ventilatory support, intraoperatively or within 30 days following surgery. Research shows that UIs are associated with elevated rates of patient mortality. This project's primary aim was to provide a secondary analysis of the NSQIP dataset to determine correlation between UIs and specific surgical factors based on current literature. Data from the NSQIP dataset were examined between 2017 and 2019 to provide the most recent information while minimizing the influence of COVID-related effects. Choice of variables was based on findings from the literature review. This study should serve as a guide for future, more extensive investigations to guide practice.

Keywords: unplanned intubations (UIs), unintended intubations (UIs), National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP), surgical factors

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	3
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	4
Overview.....	4
Unintended Intubations.....	5
Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubation.....	6
Intraoperative Factors Linked with Unplanned Intubations	6
Length of Surgery	8
Blood Loss and Transfusions.....	10
Type of Surgery	11
Cardiothoracic Surgery.....	12
Neurosurgery.....	14
Head and Neck Surgery	15
Spreading Awareness.....	18
Anesthesia Practitioner Education	18
THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.....	20
Identify the Triggering Issue.....	21
State the Purpose.....	21
First Decision Point: Is This a Priority?.....	21
Form a Team.....	22
Appraise and Synthesize Existing Knowledge	22
Decision Point Two: Is There Sufficient Evidence?.....	23
Design and Evaluation of the Practice Change.....	23
Decision Point Three: Is Change Appropriate for Adoption in Practice?	24
Integration and Dissemination	25
METHODS.....	26

Project Timeline.....	26
Design	26
Institutional Support.....	27
Ethical Considerations and Data Safety Management Plan.....	27
Setting and Participants.....	28
Data Collection	28
Secondary Data Analysis	29
Data Analysis	31
Methods of Evaluation.....	32
 RESULTS	 33
ACS-NISQIP Data	33
Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences	33
Principle Anesthesia Technique.....	33
Total Operation Time.....	34
Return to Operating Room.....	35
Bleeding Occurrences & Transfusions	35
Surgical Specialties	35
Cardiac	36
Thoracic	36
Neurosurgery.....	37
Head and Neck (ENT)	37
 DISCUSSION.....	 38
Principle Anesthesia Technique.....	39
Total Operation Time.....	40
Return to Operating Room.....	41
Bleeding Occurrences/Transfusions	41
Surgical Specialties	42
Recommendations.....	45
Limitations	46
 REFERENCES	 48
APPENDIX A: Figure 1: Comprehensive Literature Review	57
APPENDIX B: Figure 2: Iowa Model.....	58
APPENDIX C: Permission to use the Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care.....	59
APPENDIX D: Table 1: Project Timeline.....	60
APPENDIX E: CSUF IRB Approval	61

APPENDIX F: KP IRB Approval.....	62
APPENDIX G: Table 2: ACS-NSQIP Surgical Variables	63
APPENDIX H: Query Letter to JCA	64
APPENDIX I: Permission to Submit Manuscript to JCA	65
APPENDIX J: Figure 3: ACS-NSQIP Data from 2017 to 2019	66
APPENDIX K: Table 3: Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2017	67
APPENDIX L: Table 4: Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2018.....	68
APPENDIX M: Table 5: Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2019.....	69
APPENDIX N: Table 6: Study Characteristics of Surgical Specialties	70
APPENDIX O: Figure 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2017	71
APPENDIX P: Figure 5: Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2018.....	72
APPENDIX Q: Figure 6: Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2019	73
APPENDIX R: Figure 7: Multivariate Logistic Regression for Cardiac.....	74
APPENDIX S: Figure 8: Multivariate Logistic Regression for Thoracic	75
APPENDIX T: Figure 9: Multivariate Logistic Regression for Neurosurgery	76
APPENDIX U: Figure 10: Multivariate Logistic Regression for ENT	77
APPENDIX V: Manuscript submitted to <i>Journal of Clinical Anesthesia</i>	78

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Background

Identifying and avoiding preventable perioperative airway complications are essential elements of providing safe anesthesia. Organizations such as the American College of Surgeons (ACS) have created programs such as the National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) with the aim to collect data and help reduce surgical complications that result in significant patient morbidity and mortality (Gabriel et al., 2017). Collecting patient safety-related data allows institutions to track surgical complications to analyze and fix problem areas in order to improve patient safety (ACS, 2021). One area of appreciable morbidity and mortality is the occurrence of unplanned intubations (UIs) (Brovman et al., 2017). According to ACS-NSQIP, UIs are defined as a circumstance that requires the unanticipated placement of an endotracheal tube or similar device, such as the laryngeal mask airway (LMA) or nasotracheal tube with ventilatory support, intraoperatively or within 30 days following surgery (Brovman et al., 2017). Unplanned intubation also refers to intubation following failed extubation (Chen et al., 2021). Indications for UI can vary and include both patient-related factors as well as surgical-related factors (Chen et al., 2021). Previous research has shown that surgical risk factors play an essential role in predicting UIs. For the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) scholarly project, a secondary data analysis of the ACS-NSQIP database will be undertaken to explore the surgical factors affecting UIs, including the number and occurrences of unplanned intubations, total operative time, and type of surgery performed.

Problem Statement

Despite advances in healthcare, various surgical factors continue to be associated with critical patient complications that are associated with UIs. According to Burton, Khoche, A'court, et al. (2018), surgical factors contribute to 16% of postoperative complications resulting

in pulmonary compromise. Furthermore, postoperative pulmonary complications requiring UI have been shown to be associated with a four-fold increase in patient morbidity and mortality in the 30 days following surgery (Brovman et al., 2017; Burton, Khoche, A'Court, et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). Existing research shows that UIs occur at about a 3% rate; however, the associated mortality rate for the UI patient population ranges from 31-71% (Hua et al., 2012). Although the occurrence of UIs is relatively low, the mortality rate of patients requiring UI is high. For this reason, further investigation of the risk factors associated with UIs is of paramount importance to reduce patient morbidity and mortality and alleviate the economic burden placed on the healthcare systems.

In addition to the increased morbidity and mortality associated with UIs, there is a nine to ten-fold increase in hospital cost to care for patients that require an UI (Brovman et al., 2017; Burton, Khoche, A'Court et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). Unplanned intubations and their sequelae cost the United States healthcare system an estimated \$1.96 billion dollars annually (Burton, Khoche, A'Court, et al., 2018). Previous studies have tried creating risk calculators to predict possible UIs, combining various factors such as patient comorbidities, functional and physical status, and surgical factors. Although studies have identified some risk factors for UI, the specific surgical causes have yet to be thoroughly investigated.

Various studies have linked specific patient factors such as age, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status, comorbidities, functional dependence, and functional status to UIs. However, surgical factors resulting in UI are largely under-investigated, which contributes to a lack of knowledge regarding patient safety during the perioperative period. Due to the significant patient liability associated with surgical procedures, it is imperative that surgical factors affecting UIs are identified, with safety measures enacted to prevent patient

harm. Unplanned intubations are significant adverse events that increase the average hospital length of stay, hospital costs, and the risk of developing pneumonia (Chen et al., 2021).

Considering the overall financial and public health implications of UIs, it is clear that understanding the surgical risk factors associated with UIs is essential to improving the overall perioperative morbidity and mortality of surgical patients, as well as reducing healthcare costs (Li et al., 2020).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this scholarly project was to identify the surgical factors associated with UIs within the perioperative hospital setting, which would serve to enhance the knowledge base and awareness of anesthesia providers of surgical risk factors that can potentially result in UI for the surgical population. The primary aim of the study was to conduct a secondary analysis of the ACS-NSQIP dataset to identify correlations between surgical factors and UIs. Secondary aims included developing a publishable manuscript based on the results of the secondary data analysis and making recommendations on how to address those surgical factors found to contribute to UIs.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature review was conducted to provide the foundation for this scholarly project. The purpose of the literature review was to investigate if there is an association between surgical factors and UIs based on previous studies. The key terms and concepts used to search the databases include “unplanned,” “unintended,” “intubations,” “reintubations,” “surgery,” “surgical factors,” “respiratory distress,” “respiratory failure,” “perioperative,” “intraoperative,” and “postoperative.” Search inclusion criteria were limited to peer-reviewed publications from 2015 to the present and articles published in the English language. CINAHL, PubMed, EBSCOhost, and Google Scholar were the electronic databases used in this literature review to identify relevant research and publications. Filters were applied to ensure the results produced articles from peer-reviewed journals. However, the search had to be expanded to include the last ten years due to a scarcity of relevant publications. Advanced filters, including “Full Text,” “Clinical Trial,” and “Randomized Controlled Trial,” were then applied to narrow the search. The results based on the search terms yielded 612 articles which were then narrowed to 32 retrospective cohort studies that were used in this literature review shown in Appendix A.

Although the studies presented in this integrative literature review varied in purpose, design, and sample type, each publication highlighted useful information relating to UIs. Overall, the literature yielded a lack of research isolating specific surgical factors associated with UIs, underscoring the need for this DNP scholarly project. Much of the current research explores various patient-related factors, including sex, age, ASA physical status, functional status, and comorbidities, in combination with surgical factors. According to Burton, Khoche, A’Court, et al. (2018), there are few studies that assessed perioperative risk factors relating to UIs. The term

perioperative is commonly defined as any period around the time of surgery; thus, it can include the pre-, intra-, and postoperative time points. This review will focus on the intraoperative and postoperative periods as they relate to UIs because surgical factors very rarely impact preoperative periods related to surgical patients. It is worth noting that recent literature associated with UIs and the intraoperative period is somewhat limited. Therefore, the date range for the literature search dedicated to the intraoperative period was widened to include studies from the last ten years to appropriately address this subtopic's breadth. Taken together, the literature review defined and highlighted the prevalence of UIs.

Unintended Intubations

There is a clear and well-established association between UIs and adverse patient outcomes secondary to increased patient morbidity and mortality (Beverly et al., 2016). Tillquist et al. (2016) evaluated over 13,000 UI cases and determined that 77% of reintubations were preventable, warranting an urgent need to identify the risk factors that contribute to UI. However, to properly analyze and explore surgical risk factors for UIs, an operational definition of UIs must first be established.

The most widely accepted definition of UIs comes from ACS-NSQIP, defining UIs as an unanticipated event that requires placement of an advanced airway, such as an endotracheal tube or laryngeal mask airway (LMA), occurring during the intraoperative period or within 30 days following a surgical procedure (Brovman et al., 2017). Included in this definition are reintubations due to cardiac arrest, extubations requiring reintubations, or intubation during the postoperative period for hemodynamic concerns. Excluded from this definition are patients with a chronic tracheostomy who require intermittent ventilator support, reintubation for both planned and unplanned returns to the operating room, and intubations by anesthesia during intraoperative

conversions from an unsecured airway, such as an LMA, to a secured airway (Beverly et al., 2016). Using the ACS-NSQIP definition of UIs, the parameters are clearly identified, and the event becomes easily reportable; therefore, UIs have been widely adopted as an outcome measure for quality improvement (Karamanos et al., 2016). The benchmark measurement in determining UIs utilized by the literature found in this review also stems from the ACS-NSQIP standard of reintubation within 30 days of a surgical procedure.

Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubation

The overall synthesis of evidence has demonstrated that unraveling surgical factors connected to unplanned intubations is a high priority but can be challenging to ascertain. For the purposes of this scholarly project, surgical factors will be defined as perioperative elements that are directly influenced by the surgery itself, including surgical specialties (i.e., the type of surgery performed on the patient), total operative time (in hours and minutes), anesthesia technique (as some surgeries dictate the type of anesthesia that is appropriate), and surgical complications (respiratory distress, surgical blood loss, and respiratory failure) related to UIs. After performing a literature review, if there was a trend noted between certain surgical factors and UIs, this DNP scholarly project focused its secondary data analysis on only relevant variables by gleaning the information from the literature or determining a gap in the published evidence. Based on the literature, several surgical factors associated with UIs were identified, including surgical considerations within the perioperative period, such as intraoperative factors, length of surgery, and type of surgery.

Intraoperative Factors Linked with Unplanned Intubations

Upon examination of recent literature, intraoperative factors contributing to UIs are not well studied or understood. The majority of existing data reflects UIs occurring during the

postoperative period. Nonetheless, it is necessary to explore which intraoperative factors, if any, play a role in UIs during any phase of the perioperative period. Given the limited amount of recent data, the date range for qualifying articles was expanded to include studies published from 2010 to present in order to explore this subtopic adequately.

The intraoperative period is defined by many as the point at which the patient enters the surgical suite until the patient exits the surgical suite (Jaffe et al., 2019). This includes the induction and emergence of anesthesia as well as the total operative or surgical time (Jaffe et al., 2019). Chau-In et al. (2006) was the first ACS-NSQIP database review examining factors associated with UIs during the intraoperative and postoperative period. In this study, 58.1% of UIs occurred in the PACU, which is comparable to other more recent studies (Chau-In et al., 2006). What is unique about this study is that it also examined UIs in the intraoperative setting as well. The highest incidence of UIs occurred between 1-3 hours after surgery (54.9%), while the lowest incidence of UIs took place during the intraoperative period (12.9%) (Chau-In et al., 2006). Of those instances that qualified as an UI, 41.9% of patients had upper airway obstruction, 51.6% experienced inadequate ventilation, and 29% were hemodynamically unstable (Chau-In et al., 2006). Upper airway obstruction was defined as laryngeal edema (41.9%), secretions (6.5%), and laryngospasm (3.2%) (Chau-In et al., 2006). The three aforementioned categories that can be considered upper airway obstruction accounted for the most significant risk factors for UI (Chau-In et al., 2006). In summary, airway compromise, inadequate ventilation, and hemodynamic instability were the primary causes of intraoperative UIs, most of which can be considered patient-related, not surgical. This study is helpful because it highlights the key intraoperative components contributing to UIs.

Patient and surgical factors have been combined to help predict the chance of an UI; however, current risk index tools are outdated. Hua et al. (2012) created a risk index scoring system that takes into account both patient factors as well as surgical factors to create a screening tool to help predict the chance of UI. The screening tool, known as The Unplanned Intubation Risk Index, is comprised of four categories (Hua et al., 2012). The first three categories are considered patient factors and are as follows: age, ASA class, and the preoperative diagnosis of sepsis (Hua et al., 2012). The last category, total operative time, is considered an intraoperative, surgical factor affecting UIs (Hua et al., 2012). The data utilized by Hua et al. 2012 was compiled from the ACS-NSQIP but was from data almost ten years old. The risk assessment tool was created to predict UI within 30 days of surgery, which is consistent with the operational definition of UI outlined by ACS-NSQIP (Hua et al., 2012). Total operative time has been demonstrated to be a significant risk factor for UI, especially surgical time greater than 360 minutes (Hua et al., 2012). Although risk indices help reduce perioperative morbidity and mortality and can be helpful in preoperative planning, this tool was based on older data. Hua et al. (2012) highlight the importance of the length of surgery as an intraoperative risk factor for UI, and the subsequent research conducted on this topic expands on this assertion; however, a more recent analysis of the ACS-NSQIP data is warranted.

Length of Surgery

There is mounting evidence that suggests the length of surgery is a significant independent risk factor for UIs, regardless of the surgery being performed. More specifically, surgeries lasting greater than 360 minutes represent a considerable risk factor for the reporting of UIs, with all surgeries lasting over 1 hour in duration corresponding with a time-dependent increased risk for reintubation (Kim et al., 2018). To determine risk factors for UIs, Tillquist et

al. (2016) analyzed nearly 3 million surgical cases from the National Anesthesia Clinical Outcomes Registry (NACOR) from 2010 to 2014. Their study supports that throughout all types of surgical procedures, surgeries lasting longer than 60 minutes were significantly more likely to be associated with reintubations when compared to shorter cases. Furthermore, the risk of reintubation appears to be positively correlated to the procedure duration, as cases with the highest duration (lasting over 360 minutes) represented the highest risk (Tillquist et al., 2016). In their retrospective cohort study of 315,000 surgical cases, Brovman et al. (2017) reported that reintubated patients, on average, had significantly longer surgeries, with a mean case duration of 280 minutes compared to a mean of 200 minutes in patients who were not reintubated. However, due to these studies including various other factors, such as patient demographics, the association between surgical factors and UIs are yet to be discovered. A more recent analysis of surgical time could help elicit richer information or a change in the amount of time required to be considered a factor for UIs

Current evidence supports a positive correlation between the complexity of the procedure with the length of the procedure. In a cross-sectional study of 12,000 surgical cases, Costa (2017) evaluated the average operating room time across multiple surgical specialties to determine the surgical specialty with the greatest average case length. The study identified head and neck surgeries followed by cardiovascular surgeries as the specialties with the lengthiest procedures, with an average operative time of 202 minutes and 189 minutes, respectively. These procedures, along with neurological procedures, were also identified as being the most complex types of procedures, determined by the overall risk of the surgery, invasiveness, and average recovery time as critical factors (Costa, 2017). This data explains why cardiothoracic, head and neck, and neurological surgeries are commonly studied in the literature concerning UIs as they are often

the lengthiest and most complex procedures on average; therefore, these procedures were included in this review for further analysis.

Aside from the complexity of the procedure, the literature confirms other independent factors associated with an increased surgery length. For instance, Haskins et al. (2018) identified the surgeon's experience as a significant factor related to the length of surgery. Cases involving a surgical resident reflected an increase in the average surgical duration and increased the likelihood of negative postoperative outcomes. The average operative time for surgeries with resident involvement was 137 minutes compared to surgeries with no resident involvement at 110 minutes, resulting in a 27-minute increase in procedure length if a surgical resident was present for the procedure. The increases observed in procedure length were also accompanied by an overall increase in postoperative complications, with UIs being one of the complications that could occur (Haskins et al., 2018). From this data, whether it is due to the type of surgery (indicating the overall risk of the surgery, invasiveness, and average recovery time as critical factors), or resident involvement, there is strong evidence to suggest that type and length of the procedure are significant independent risk factors related to UIs and were therefore included in the secondary data analysis.

Blood Loss and Transfusions

Evidence suggests substantial blood loss as a risk factor for reporting a UI. A retrospective cohort study of 400 cases reported determined that an estimated blood loss greater than 300 milliliters significantly increased the risk of a subsequent UI (Kim et al., 2018). However, this article had a small sample size of 400 cases; therefore, a more comprehensive analysis from the ACS-NSQIP dataset is warranted. If blood loss becomes large enough or a patient requires platelets or clotting factors, then a blood transfusion may be necessary. Multiple

studies have confirmed an association between the need for a blood transfusion and a subsequent UI (Chen et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2018). This risk factor appears to be independent of the amount of blood that is being lost, as patients with minimal blood loss that had received a blood transfusion also had an increased risk for a UI (Chen et al., 2021).

Taken together, studies discussed above highlight that the length of surgery and the need for transfusions as distinct surgical-specific risk factors for UI that can occur with any type of surgery. Exploration of more recent data that encompasses larger numbers of surgical cases that have been assembled from across the globe would greatly aid in developing a thorough understanding of current surgical risk factors related to UIs, with a primary goal of disseminating high-quality information to prevent UIs and adverse patient outcomes.

Type of Surgery

Adverse pulmonary complications can increase the length of hospitalization and further patient morbidity and mortality risks. Unplanned intubations are a concern for any surgery, especially cardiothoracic, head and neck, and neurosurgery cases (Burton, Khoche, A'Court, et al., 2018; Gabriel et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020;). Many of these types of surgeries are linked with an increased risk of unplanned reoperations due to surgical complications, which can result in UIs. Unplanned reoperations (URs) are defined as subsequent unscheduled operations related to surgeries performed within two months of the primary operation (Kim et al., 2018). Therefore, the identification of the types of surgeries that carry the greatest risk of URs is imperative to understanding the phenomenon of UIs and minimizing perioperative complications that result in increased patient morbidity and mortality.

Cardiothoracic Surgery.

In a retrospective observational study, Beverly et al. (2016) utilized information compiled from the 2007-2013 ACS-NSQIP dataset. They found that the incidence of UIs after cardiothoracic surgery was present at a rate of 4%. Of the 4%, 3.6% were associated with lung resection within 30 days of surgery (Burton, Khoche, A'Court, et al., 2018). Unplanned intubations associated with lung resection occurred within 24 hours postoperatively in 23% of the patients studied (Burton, Khoche, A'Court, et al., 2018). Furthermore, UIs linked with cardiac-specific surgeries, such as valvular repairs most frequently occurring within four days of surgery, had a 53% incidence rate (Beverly et al., 2016). The impact of cardiothoracic surgeries on UIs demonstrates the significance in the type of surgery contributing to the frequency of UIs, but the advent of newer surgical approaches should be investigated further. In a case-control study, Chen et al. (2021) identified thoracic surgery (as well as head and neck surgery) as a significant risk factor connected to UIs due to iatrogenic complications such as phrenic nerve damage and recurrent laryngeal nerve damage. It should be noted that both of these nerves innervate the diaphragm and vocal cords, playing a significant role in the patient's ability to control their airway and breathe. Often, many of these complications required subsequent reoperations to correct the problem. Moreover, a retrospective study by Jungquist et al. (2017) supported thoracic surgeries and any other surgeries with large incisions lead to inadequate postoperative ventilation secondary to pain. Ultimately, this data contributes to the expectation that cardiothoracic surgeries have a higher incidence of resultant pulmonary complications and subsequent UI; however, a more thorough analysis using recent ACS-NSQIP data would aid in clarification of the association between cardiothoracic surgeries and UIs.

The complexity of cardiothoracic surgeries is strongly due to the potential complications that can occur during and around these surgeries. Common complications of cardiothoracic surgeries include bleeding, infection, pneumonia, cardiac tamponade, respiratory failure, and arrhythmias which can also result in increased incidences of UIs (Huston et al., 2020). Not only are UIs commonly linked with cardiothoracic surgeries, but URs can also occur. Both UIs and URs require unplanned instrumentation of the airway and are connected with multiple adverse complications. In a retrospective, observational cohort study, Crawford et al. (2017) reported that 44% of cardiac operations resulted in URs. Furthermore, bleeding from postoperative hemorrhage was reported as one of the primary concerns for patient morbidity and mortality (Crawford et al., 2017). Thus, as previously noted, the incidence of transfusions should be examined when exploring more recent ACS-NSQIP data. Thoracotomies associated with a mediastinal approach commonly exhibit excessive bleeding, cardiac tamponade, infection, and death (Crawford et al., 2017). It was determined that multi-factorial intraoperative complications can occur in cardiothoracic procedures; therefore, this type of surgery should be examined for the incidence of UIs. In a separate study by Al-Attar et al. (2019), the authors support that the complex nature of cardiothoracic surgery can be associated with increased risk for complications, especially postoperative hemorrhage. The intricacies of cardiothoracic surgeries present many patient risks and myriad potential complications associated with the surgical procedure itself. Not surprising, UIs are one of the complications seen throughout the literature. These types of surgeries are associated with intraoperative factors associated with damage to surrounding anatomy (such as the phrenic nerve) and also postoperative factors linked to respiratory failure and bleeding (which necessitate immediate surgical interventions and URs to locate and control the complications).

Neurosurgery.

Similar to cardiothoracic surgery, the literature demonstrates that neurosurgery also has an increased incidence of UIs. In a retrospective cohort study, Burton, Lin, A'Court, et al. (2018) analyzed elective spine surgery from the ACS-NSQIP dataset from 2007 to 2017 and found a 0.5% incidence of UIs from the sample size of 26,263. However, there was a 26% incidence of UI when factoring in patients with functional dependence and increased comorbidities. Unfortunately, whether the surgery was emergent or elective was not explored (Burton, Lin, A'Court, et al., 2018). Clearly, further information must be collected on whether emergent cases impact the rate of UIs. Additionally, patients undergoing cervical spine surgery had a 13% incidence of respiratory complications, more than any other organ system (Burton, Lin, A'Court, et al., 2018). This can be due to damage to vital structures within the cervical region of the neck, which is important for respiration. These structures include cervical bones (C1 to C7), cartilages (cricoid and thyroid), the carotid sheath (common carotid and internal carotid arteries, internal jugular vein, lymphatic plexus and cranial nerves IX-XII), and both superficial and deep fascial layers (investing, pre-tracheal, and pre-vertebral) (Debkowska et al., 2019). Damage to the aforementioned structures may lead to UIs secondary to the formation of hematomas, nerve impairment that innervate the vocal cords, and damage to thyroid or cricoid cartilage located at C4 and C6 (respectively). In another retrospective cohort study by Li et al. (2020), data from the ACS-NSQIP database between the years 2012 to 2015 found the rate of UI was 2.3% for patients who underwent craniotomy for brain tumor removal. Within the patient population that suffered UI, 76.4% experienced major adverse events, including infection of the surgical site, pulmonary embolism, stroke, cardiac arrest, deep venous thrombosis (DVT), seizures, sepsis, and septic shock (Burton, Lin, A'Court, et al., 2018; Nobis et al., 2020). This underscores the severity of

concomitant adverse effects that can be devastating for patients, as well as increased cost of treatment and prolonged hospitalization. Many of the neurosurgical adverse events are associated with respiratory complications, especially respiratory compromise secondary to pulmonary embolism, DVT, seizures, and forms of sepsis leading to UIs and URs. Likewise, the emergent nature of a procedure should also be examined for association with UIs. Thus, neurosurgical surgeries should be included in any analysis of UIs, as well as whether or not the case was an emergency.

Neurosurgical cases tend to have frequent URs, between 4% and 8%, due to the increased difficulty of surgical intervention (Sangal et al., 2018). Unplanned reoperations can be attributed to surgical site infections and overall length of stay (Molina et al., 2019). More specifically, complications related to external ventricle drainage (EVD), including infection and clot obstruction, and postoperative hemorrhage, were the primary and secondary reasons for reoperation, respectively (Molina et al., 2019). These complications can cause seizures resulting in respiratory depression and patient compromise leading to subsequent UIs (Burton, Lin, A'Court, et al., 2018; Nobis et al., 2020). Although the occurrence of UI in neurosurgery is lower than in cardiothoracic surgeries, evidence suggests positive correlations between UIs and neurosurgical procedures, and thus supports the importance of understanding the relationship using current ACS-NSQIP data.

Head and Neck Surgery.

As alluded to by Chen et al. (2021), head and neck surgery (also known as ear, nose, and throat (ENT) surgery) similarly has a high prevalence of UIs. Although head and neck procedures are not considered as high-risk as cardiothoracic or neurosurgery cases, the literature suggests there is a link to UIs. In a retrospective cohort study, Gabriel et al. (2017) analyzed

ACS-NSQIP data from 2007 to 2013 regarding thyroid- and parathyroidectomies. These authors reported a link with UIs related to airway compromise, such as surgical hematoma, recurrent laryngeal nerve injury, and hypocalcemia-induced laryngospasm. Their findings highlight the harmful adverse events that can lead to increased patient morbidity and mortality. Within their analysis of the ACS-NSQIP data, 3.3% of thyroid- and parathyroidectomies were linked with UIs within 30 days of surgery (Gabriel et al., 2017). The literature validates the implication that head and neck surgeries can contribute to the prevalence of UIs through unfavorable surgical complications and respiratory compromise. As mentioned in the neurosurgical section above, there are many essential respiratory structures within the head and neck regions. Damage to any of the structures disposes the patient to increased risk of UIs and URs secondary to respiratory complications, including tissue and nerve damage leading to inflammation, swelling, and infection. Therefore, a more in-depth analysis of the relationship between head and neck surgeries and UIs is warranted.

Head and neck surgeries carry an increased risk of complications related to UIs. Unplanned reoperations have been frequently associated with not only UIs but also significant patient morbidity and mortality. According to Sangal et al. (2018), the rate of URs for head and neck surgery was 14.2%, higher than any other studied surgical field. This emphasizes that critical intraoperative complications can occur from head and neck surgeries, indicating that this type of surgery should be thoroughly studied for the correlation to UIs. Per analyzed results using the ACS-NSQIP data between 2005 to 2014, patients that underwent laryngectomy had a 12.4% increased risk of reoperations, which was associated with increased risk of UIs (Sangal et al., 2018). Head and neck surgeries have been connected with surgical site infection due to the increased risk of superficial and deep surgical infections caused by postoperative complications

such as airway inflammation (Sangal et al., 2018). Swelling of the airway results in immediate acute airway compromise leading to UIs to protect the patient's lungs, which reiterates the importance of further investigating the connection between head and neck surgeries to UIs (Chen et al., 2021).

Taken together, UIs, and their sequelae, have been clearly defined in this review as markers for severe adverse perioperative health outcomes. Although the incidence of UI is relatively low (3%), the associated morbidity and mortality is roughly 50%, indicating the devastating effects UI can have on a patient (Brovman et al., 2017; Hua et al., 2012). For this reason, further investigation into the surgical factors affecting UIs is paramount. The literature suggests that surgical factors affecting UIs include the length of surgery, type of surgery, and perioperative blood loss; however, some studies are outdated and not always based on global data with large patient cohorts. This DNP scholarly project utilized a secondary data analysis of ACS-NSQIP data to further explore the relationship between the aforementioned surgical factors and UIs. It focused on recent surgical data and included a large patient sample from across the world. Due to its low cost and accessibility, secondary data analysis via the ACS-NSQIP database is an appropriate means of data collection (Dunn et al., 2015). This exploratory analysis helped identify surgical factors related to UIs and was then disseminated as recommendations via a publishable manuscript. Research has shown that manuscripts are a valuable method of information dissemination for the purposes of clinical practice and quality improvement (Becker et al., 2018; Broome, 2018). There is a clear knowledge gap regarding current surgical factors and their effect on UIs. In addition, morbidity and mortality related to UIs are very high. For these reasons, a publishable manuscript that expands the body of knowledge associated with UIs, and educates healthcare providers at the clinical level could help improve surgical outcomes.

Spreading Awareness

One of the initial steps in spreading awareness to anesthesia practitioners is ensuring that the findings are appropriately and effectively shared with the healthcare community.

Dissemination is an essential aspect of healthcare improvement because any findings that are not shared will have little impact on practice and patient outcomes. One of the primary goals of the DNP graduate, per the American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN) DNP Essentials (AACN, 2022), is to translate research into practice and disseminate new knowledge (Becker et al., 2018). Current literature has demonstrated that disseminating scholarly work through manuscript publication is a method by which DNP graduates can translate evidence into practice (Becker et al., 2018). The use of manuscripts for dissemination is not new and has been used by other educational specialties, including geography, sociology, and science, especially health sciences (Broome, 2018). Furthermore, the rationale for choosing a manuscript to disseminate knowledge is to portray the skills of doctorate-prepared nurses (Broome, 2018). One of the principle aims of this scholarly project was to fulfill this AACN DNP requirement and further contribute to the body of knowledge related to UIs.

Anesthesia Practitioner Education

A publishable manuscript can serve as a vehicle for disseminating knowledge and potential recommendations supported by evidence. The goal of this scholarly DNP project was to provide a thorough summary of evidence regarding surgical factors linked with UIs and offer evidence-based recommendations to improve patient outcomes (Becker et al., 2018). According to Becker et al., 2018, educational manuscripts are a valuable means of disseminating information. For this reason, the goal of this project was to create a publishable manuscript to

further the body of knowledge related to UIs, educate anesthesia providers, and improve surgical outcomes. While the dissemination of evidence alone may not lead to changes in the clinical realm, disseminating the evidence and knowledge from this scholarly project through a publishable manuscript can increase awareness, which may ultimately lead to practice change (Melynk, 2016).

The manuscript for surgical factors linked with UIs aimed to provide accurate, clear, and concise information to anesthesia practitioners. The literature also demonstrates several different methods to disseminate evidence (book chapters and presentations); however, through publication, the findings of this scholarly project can be shared globally with the healthcare and scientific community, where others can adopt and further investigate surgical factors associated with UIs (Liang et al. 2017). Publishable manuscripts are an important means by which knowledge transfer and dissemination can be achieved in the academic community (Oermann & Hays, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

The Iowa Model of Research in Practice to Promote Quality Care was selected as the theoretical framework to guide this DNP scholarly project (Appendix B). The Iowa Model serves as a template for clinicians, educators, administrators, researchers, and most specifically, nurses and healthcare providers to guide the implementation of research findings into practice (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017; Lloyd et al., 2016). The original Iowa Model was developed by Marita Titler, who identified conditions that would evoke practice advances by having healthcare providers incorporate evidence from research into practice for quality improvement (Titler et al., 1994). By doing so, evidence-based practice (EBP) became a scaffold for clinically relevant initiatives. Evidence-based practice is defined as the application of research evidence in combination with clinical expertise and patients' preferences when making medical decisions (Chiwaula et al., 2021). The Iowa Model has since been revised in 2015 to reflect on the expansion of successful strategies in utilizing research and introducing change to the health community (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

The Iowa Model provides a roadmap to help evidence-based practice teams in identifying triggering issues, stating the question or purpose, forming a team, appraising and synthesizing relevant literature, creating and integrating proposed solutions, evaluating improvements, sustaining the changes, and disseminating the results shown in Appendix B (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Furthermore, the Iowa Model has integrated decision points and feedback loops that guide healthcare providers on whether to proceed or to conduct additional research and redesign the proposed practice change. Following the Iowa Model, once the clinical problem has been identified, a comprehensive literature review can guide the direction of the scholarly project regarding the relationship between the variables, in this case, surgical factors and UIs, as well as

evidence supporting solutions to this phenomenon. After a solution has been identified, recommendations for changes can be created, evaluated, and disseminated. Approval was granted by the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics to use their Iowa Model (Appendix C).

Identify the Triggering Issue

The Iowa Model's first step is to identify a clinical problem that needs to be solved, which helps determine the project's purpose (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The limited studies regarding the prevalence of surgical factors associated with UIs indicated a gap in the literature that warranted further investigation. The triggering issue for this scholarly DNP project centered around UIs and the clinical link between surgical factors. Following the Iowa Model, the literature was used to investigate the relationship between surgical factors associated with UIs.

State the Purpose

In step two of the Iowa Model, the project's purpose statement is determined and formally stated. Formulating a purpose statement narrows the focus of a project, keeping the team engaged while also providing direction (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). A clearly defined purpose statement also helps with subsequent decision points, as the purpose statement forms the basis of all gathered research and evidence.

First Decision Point: Is This a Priority?

An important step within the Iowa Model framework is determining whether a project is a priority. In this step, priority is assessed by considering several key aspects, which include the scope of the problem, the impact on patient quality of life, the economic burden, and the relevance to current practice settings (Cullen et al., 2017). Priority is established once these key considerations are evaluated and determined to have been satisfactorily met. For this project,

priority was established as the topic of UIs has a significant impact on patient quality of life and is considered highly relevant to current anesthesia practice settings.

Form a Team

Once the purpose statement is formed and determined to be a priority, a team is then formed, which will include all key players that are required for the project. Cullen et al. (2017) identified six factors necessary for a successful team which included location, size of the team, composition, communication, stability, and leadership. Successful teamwork will then assist in moving the change process at a faster pace and can help maintain a positive group attitude. For this DNP project, members were selected based on having the necessary skill sets needed to plan, implement, and evaluate the project. The team is composed of the project's authors (DNP Student Registered Nurse Anesthetists), a Ph.D. Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (CRNA) faculty team lead, a Ph.D. Registered Nurse (RN) faculty team member, librarian support, the Kaiser Permanente (KP) Quality Safety and Regulatory Oversight Department (QSROD), Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Regional Research Statistical Support (R2S2), and any other associated expert faculty that supports the project.

Appraise and Synthesize Existing Knowledge

Following the formation of a team, a search for the current literature is done by appraising articles and synthesizing the evidence found in the research. Cullen et al. (2017) stated that the appraisal of high-quality evidence begins with searching through a reliable and reputable databases such as PubMed and CINAHL. The evidence is then weighed to determine relevancy and strength. For this project, the relevancy and strength of the evidence was assessed within the table of evidence (TOE). Once the appraisal of all articles was complete, the evidence was synthesized in a review of the literature. The review of literature for this project followed the

steps required to attain and appraise the available high-quality evidence relevant to surgical factors contributing to UIs. Following the review of literature, evidence was found to support the project's purpose, thus directing the next step in the Iowa Model (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Decision Point Two: Is There Sufficient Evidence?

After a review of the existing literature, it was determined that there is a gap in evidence related to surgical factors affecting UIs. This topic did not have a sufficient body of evidence to support a definitive practice change to address the clinical problem of UIs during the perioperative period. Therefore, the aforementioned team formulated a plan to address this clinical problem. This project focused on producing a publishable manuscript on surgical factors that might contribute to UIs. Research has shown that published manuscripts are very influential in the clinical arena and an excellent strategy for communicating clinical expertise, practice recommendations, and innovations in healthcare practice with fellow healthcare providers (Oermann & Hays, 2018).

Design and Evaluation of the Practice Change

The next step in the Iowa Model is the "Design and Evaluation of the Practice Change" section, and this is when the team creates an intervention designed to bring about a change in practice (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). To address this section of the Iowa Model, future work (undertaken by another DNP team) would incorporate the findings from the secondary data analysis of ACS-NSQIP and model them into a clinically based intervention. Recommendations from this scholarly DNP project were suggested to guide future DNP teams to design interventions, including the use of preoperative screening checklists, risk assessment screening tools, or preoperative risk indices aimed at early recognition of patients at risk of UI. These

future practice change interventions would incorporate the greatest risk factors for UIs identified through evaluation of the ACS-NSQIP database. Risk assessment tools and risk indices could be produced to help clinicians prevent UIs. Research in areas such as cardiology and psychology have demonstrated that risk assessment tools produce results with a high level of sensitivity and specificity (Delgadillo et al., 2018). Clinicians could incorporate preoperative screening tools or postoperative checklists in order to identify high-risk patients, optimize the patient or surgery and ultimately reduce the incidence of UIs.

Another key component of this section of the Iowa Model is evaluation of the project's intervention (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Evaluation could be achieved through post-implementation surveys administered to multidisciplinary members of the healthcare team. Feedback could be aggregated and used for revisions of the project. Adherence to the practice change could be ensured through the utilization of nurse champions or unit champions whose role is to monitor the project's implementation. Nurse champions have been shown to assist clinicians with clinical practice changes and help promote QI project adherence (Mount & Anderson, 2015).

Decision Point Three: Is Change Appropriate for Adoption in Practice?

After developing a design and evaluating the change, the future DNP team would need to assess the adoption of their improvement project. This would depend on the method to integrate change, which can be a risk assessment tool implemented into the charting system or a handoff tool mentioned above. The tools would alert all healthcare teams and personnel pertinent to the patient for the potential of UI based on intraoperative factors such as blood loss and length of surgery, as well as the type of surgery. After the trial period, which could be for one month, retrieving stakeholder feedback could assess for adoption of the change. A survey could be

implemented to gather information on whether the tool was being employed, the ease of use, and how likely would the healthcare team implement the tool during charting and handoff. If the project yields successful results, steps could be taken to integrate new guidelines into routine practice.

Integration and Dissemination

The concluding section of the Iowa Model is titled “Integration and Dissemination.” This portion of the Iowa Model aims to identify and engage key stakeholders and personnel to affect change in the intended population (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Based on decision point three, if there is positive feedback from stakeholders, the future DNP groups could solidify and integrate the change into practice. To determine the successful integration of the improvement tool, intermittent audits of CRNA and Medical Doctor of Anesthesia (MDA) to assess adherence. If the surveys and audits do not show consistent use of the tool, reintegration sessions could be held to promote compliance (Cullen et al., 2017). During the reintegration sessions, further feedback from all stakeholders, especially anesthesia providers, should be considered to address barriers and achieve organizational adoption. Once the project exhibits sustainable positive outcomes, the future DNP teams could disseminate the findings at local and national healthcare conferences via poster presentations, oral expositions, or other vehicles of dissemination. This would facilitate education and quality improvement related to surgical factors affecting UIs for anesthesia providers and healthcare systems at large.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to identify the association between surgical factors and UIs by first performing a thorough literature review and analyzing secondary data from the ACS-NSQIP dataset. Findings of this project generated recommendations for future DNP projects to explore interventions that will alert healthcare providers of the surgical factors that put patients at increased risk of UI.

Project Timeline

Table 1 provides a visual representation of the overall timeline for this DNP project (see Appendix D). By January 2022, this DNP proposal was presented to all relevant faculty, and a consultation request to the R2S2 was made after a successful DNP proposal defense. By March, Institutional Review Board (IRB) submissions and determinations were made and completed with both the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) and California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) IRBs. Following IRB approval, the DNP project started with obtaining data related to surgical factors contributing to UIs from the ACS-NSQIP database. Once relevant data was obtained, analysis of the data occurred from April to June. From July to August, the DNP team began developing a manuscript based on the relevant findings. Then from August to November, a manuscript was written that was based on the results and recommendations gathered from the entire process. During October and November, the final DNP scholarly project was completed, a presentation was developed, and poster was created.

Design

This project used a descriptive research design to conduct a secondary data analysis of previously collected data housed in the ACS-NSQIP database, with the goal of identifying

surgical factors that contribute to UI. More specifically, a retrospective analysis of ACS-NSQIP data from 2017 to 2019 was analyzed using univariate and multivariate statistics to explore associations between surgical factors and UIs. With the results of the secondary data analysis, a manuscript and recommendations for practice change were developed.

Institutional Support

Institutional support was used throughout this scholarly project to incorporate high-quality peer-reviewed studies relevant to the project. California State University, Fullerton's library assisted in the formation of the comprehensive review to obtain studies related to the association between surgical factors and UIs. Cotton Coslett, a CSUF librarian, was consulted to provide assistance and support in finding high-quality studies by applying appropriate search terms and utilizing different search engines. Additionally, weekly meetings with the CSUF DNP and Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) faculty served to help the progression and construction of this scholarly DNP project.

Ethical Considerations and Data Safety Management Plan

Kaiser Permanente Southern California IRB and CSUF IRB approvals were obtained prior to data analysis (Appendices E & F). All data extracted from the ACS-NSQIP dataset had patient and provider identifiers removed, and all anonymous data will be kept protected on KP's secure servers prior to analysis. Once collected from the KP Quality Safety and Regulatory Oversight Department (KP-QSROD), all data will be entered into a spreadsheet on a secure and encrypted network. Data analysis will not be transferred out of KP's network and stored only on password-protected computers. Only aggregate results, no individual patient-level data, will be published or shared outside of KPSC or CSUF. Internally, data analysis will be gathered by KPSA DNP students and shared via a mutual drive with only pertinent study-related information

to those who require the information to perform their job duties. All health information not associated with this project will be removed prior to data collection. Upon completion of this scholarly project, all paper resources will be destroyed after three years.

Data security and patient privacy are of utmost importance in medical research. All members of this research team took the necessary steps to ensure data was kept safe. This included analyzing, maintaining, and housing the clinical data on KP servers to guarantee data protection. Additionally, patient data was not transferred or accessed outside of the KP electronic domain. In doing so, the research team and the ACS-NSQIP dataset upheld HIPAA compliance laws and avoided compromising patient safety or patient identity.

Setting and Participants

Data on surgical factors associated with UIs was extracted from the ACS-NSQIP dataset, which tracks surgical complications and collects data to help healthcare providers and hospitals analyze and improve surgical outcomes (ACS, 2021). The ACS-NSQIP database houses data from participating hospitals' patient medical charts and allows healthcare providers and hospitals to compare national benchmarks. Data collection and analysis took place at the KPSA offices in Pasadena, California, on KP-approved computers.

Data Collection

The examination of surgical factors that are associated with UIs was performed using the ACS-NSQIP database via secondary data analysis from years 2017 to 2019. Surgical factors that were explored included the principle anesthetic technique required for the surgery, type of surgery (i.e., surgical specialty), total operative time, presence of bleeding occurrences requiring transfusions within 72 hours of surgery start, emergent nature of the procedure, number of reoperations and number of patients that returned to the operating room (Appendix G). The KP

R2S2 provided access to the 2017 to 2019 dataset files, which include anonymized aggregate data to only pertinent study personnel.

Secondary Data Analysis

This DNP scholar project included secondary data analysis investigating associations between surgical variables and UIs. Secondary data analysis describes the utilization of existing data for the purposes of answering new research questions or testing new hypotheses (Dunn et al., 2015). Secondary data is defined as data collected by prior researchers that have been compiled into databases or large data sets (Cheng & Phillips, 2014). Using existing data previously collected from large samples drawn from various parts of the world can bring about findings that are generalizable. Additionally, analysis of available data requires significantly less time and resources while posing minimal risks to participants (Dunn et al., 2015). Because a gap in knowledge was identified through the literature review, this DNP project aimed to explore those surgical factors that were associated with UIs using a large, global dataset. By using the ACS-NSQIP dataset, the amount of time and number of resources required to explore this rare phenomenon was greatly decreased, enabling this DNP project to be executed in the time and budget available.

Nevertheless, secondary data analyses do have their limitations. In order to conduct a secondary data analysis, researchers need access to large-scale databases and must have the skill to appraise the quality of the evidence (Dunn et al., 2015). Furthermore, secondary data could be outdated due to a gap between when the data was initially collected and when secondary data analysis was performed (Dunn et al., 2015). Secondary data can be gathered from public datasets, such as that provided by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) (Dunn et al., 2015), or private datasets, such as National Trauma Data

Bank Research Dataset (NTDBRDS) (Alluri et al., 2016). Typically, private organizations own the rights to private data sets, including the American Heart Association and the National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators (NDNQI) (Dunn et al., 2015), making access costly or cumbersome to obtain. This DNP project was able to retrieve data from the ACS-NSQIP dataset because KPSC is an actively contributing entity committed to the quality improvement ACS-NSQIP hopes to foster. Secondary data analysis was a valuable strategy for this scholarly work due to the accessibility of the ACS-NSQIP database through the KP affiliation. The ACS-NSQIP provided an abundance of surgical data to support the aims of this project.

The ACS-NSQIP is a valuable resource for surgical outcome data. The American College of Surgeons was created in 1913 with the goal of improving health outcomes for patients undergoing surgery (Beesoon et al., 2020). The ACS-NSQIP uses data directly from the electronic medical record of patients and is risk-adjusted based on 30-day patient outcomes (American College of Surgeons, 2021a). “Risk-adjusted” means that data are differentiated into similar categories based on comparison models, which creates more consistent and reliable data sets (American College of Surgeons, 2021a). There has been a significant increase in publications using the ACS-NSQIP database over the last 13 years (Beesoon et al., 2020), and this can be attributed to a 38% yearly increase in the number of healthcare institutions that have incorporated ACS-NSQIP as a means of quality improvement (Beesoon et al., 2020). The ACS-NSQIP is a robust, data-rich program that provides quality clinical information (Beesoon et al., 2020). This manuscript will utilize the ACS-NSQIP database for secondary data analysis related to surgical variables in association with the prevalence of UIs shown in Appendix G.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to delineate sample characteristics and categorical variables. Patients' surgical characteristics were obtained from ACS-NSQIP for years 2017 to 2019. The frequency of UIs was determined by examining the ACS-NSQIP data variable REINTUB listed in Appendix G. Other surgical variables were compared between those patients who did and did not require reintubation for each year. The rate of UI among the different surgical variables was compared via univariate and multivariate logistic regression. For univariate analysis, characteristics of patients were reported as percentages for categorical variables, and median, interquartile (IQR), and ranges were used for continuous variables. The Chi-Square test was used to test for categorical differences in reintubated groups. Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to calculate differences on continuous variables. Multivariate logistic regression was performed, and odds ratios (ORs) and confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to detect the probability of reintubation for each year. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the collected data, while inferential statistics were used to examine associations between surgical variables and UIs. The predictive model included variables with statistically significant results, as well as univariate results with clinically meaningful differences between groups. Forest plots were produced to display the results graphically, and Wald tests were used to calculate the p -value for the ORs. The same univariate and multivariate analyses were further performed and stratified by surgery types; cardiac, otolaryngology (ENT), thoracic, and neurosurgery, with 2017 to 2019 data combined. All analyses were two-sided and performed using SAS EG 8.2 (Cary, NC). P-values of less than 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$) were considered statistically significant.

Methods of Evaluation

The deliverable of this project was to develop a manuscript that would be reviewed and evaluated for publication. The topic of the article fits well within the mission and the scope of the

Journal of Clinical Anesthesia (JCA) and would be of interest to its readership. The journal is well respected and widespread. Articles are published in this journal following a blinded peer-review process. Peer review is a powerful form of evaluation in which manuscripts can be adapted, improved, and eventually published (Oermann & Hays, 2018). A typical research article, based on the JCA guidelines for authors, should include separate sections on introduction, materials and methods, results, and discussion sections. Articles should also include relevant tables and figures, title page, abstract, references, and author information (Elsevier, n.d.). A query letter was emailed to JCA for potential publication and the decision from the journal to submit the manuscript. Please see Appendix H for query letter to JCA and Appendix I for approval to submit a manuscript.

Results

ACS-NSQIP Data

The ACS-NSQIP database included 3,087,654 surgical cases between 2017 to 2019 (Appendix J). There were 3,068,503 cases that did not result in UIs and 19,151 that were associated with UIs, with an average incidence rate of 0.62%. The variables assessed in this study are outlined in Table 2 with their respective definitions (Appendix G). Study characteristics data were organized by year (2017-2019) in Tables 3-5, with each variable of interest highlighted in respective forest plots (Figures 4-6). Please see Appendices K, L, and M for study characteristics and Appendices O, P, and Q for multivariate logistic regression for the years 2017, 2018, and 2019 respectively. Then, data were organized by surgical specialty in Figures 7-10 (Appendices R, S, T, and U). The surgical specialty data is reported as a summation of the years 2017 to 2019. Figures 4-10 include multivariate statistical analysis, including ORs and 95% CIs. Univariate data was collected as well and reported with each individual variable of interest.

Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences

As the dependent variable of interest, the incidence of UI was first calculated. Out of 1,025,582 total cases recorded in the ACS-NSQIP database in 2017, 6,840 resulted in a UI (Appendix J). This was a relatively small percentage (0.66%), which was very different compared with the existing literature on the topic. The following two years, 2018 (0.63%) and 2019 (0.57%), showed similar rates of UI within similar sample sizes (Appendix J).

Principle Anesthetic Technique

The category principle anesthetic technique (ANESTHES) was divided into groups to reflect the primary anesthetic approach provided for each surgical case, including MAC

(monitored anesthesia care) and IV (intravenous) sedation, spinal, epidural, local, and regional anesthesia. Using general anesthesia as a reference, each type of anesthesia was examined for association with the dependent variable UIs. As outlined in Tables 3-5, the “MAC/IV Sedation” category showed a statistically significant relationship with UIs ($p < 0.0001$) (Appendices K, L, M). This data was consistent over all three years (OR [95% CI] = 0.551 [0.465-0.653], 0.616 [0.524-0.725], 0.474 [0.388-0.579] for years 2017-2019, respectively) with ORs less than one, indicating a negative correlation to UIs (Appendices O, P, Q). When examining “Spinal” anesthesia as the primary anesthetic approach, all three years showed a statistically significant relationship with UIs ($p < 0.0001$). The ORs for this group demonstrated a negative correlation between “Spinal” anesthesia and UIs as well (OR [95% CI] = 0.313 [0.252-0.390], 0.281 [0.220-0.360], 0.341 [0.270-0.430]) as seen in Tables 3-5 (Appendices K, L, M).

Total Operative Time

The ACS-NSQIP variable for total operative time (OPTIME) showed statistical significance across all three years of interest ($p < 0.0001$). Total operative time was measured in minutes, comparing the total operative time for cases that did or did not result in UI. The multivariate statistics for this category showed ORs very close to 1 across all three years (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.002-1.003], 1.003 [1.002-1.003], 1.003 [1.002-1.003]) shown in Figures 4-6 (Appendices O, P, Q). Although the odds ratios do not show a strong relationship, the univariate analysis (Tables 3-5) quantifies the mean operative time for all cases for each respective year (Appendices K, L, M). In 2017, mean operative time for non-reintubated patients was 109.6 minutes compared with 178.7 minutes for those that did require reintubation. A similar relationship was present between these two groups during 2018 (110.8 minutes versus 176.6

minutes) and 2019 (111.1 min and 185.8 minutes). On average, cases that resulted in a UI were approximately one hour longer than cases that did not.

Return to Operating Room

Surgical cases that resulted in a return to the operating room (RETURNOR) were very strongly correlated with UIs ($p < 0.0001$). The multivariate statistics for this category showed strong positive correlation with UI (OR [95% CI] = 5.166 [4.856-5.496], 5.644 [5.297-6.014], 5.860 [5.484-6.261]) as seen in Tables 3-5 (Appendices K, L, M). This pattern was seen consistently in the data from 2017 to 2019.

Bleeding Occurrences & Transfusions

Bleeding occurrences requiring transfusions (OTHBLEED) was defined as transfusions of red blood cells (RBCs) within the first 72 hours of surgery start time. Tables 3-5 demonstrate statistical significance in this category across all three years of interest ($p < 0.0001$) (Appendices K, L, M). A strong positive correlation was borne out in the evidence as displayed in Figures 4-6 (OR [95% CI] = 1.940 [1.816-2.072], 1.808 [1.688-1.937], 1.810 [1.683-1.946]) (Appendices O, P, Q)

Surgical Specialties

Data included in this section were combined from 2017 to 2019 to produce an aggregate number for each individual surgical specialty. Multiple variables were examined for each surgical specialty, but only the statistically significant variables were reported. The surgical specialty data showed very similar results to previously mentioned generalized surgical data (Figures 7-10), with bleeding occurrences and operative time showing very strong correlations with UI amongst almost all the surgical specialties of interest (Appendices R, S, T, U). Neurosurgery, cardiac surgery, ENT surgery, and thoracic surgery were all examined

independently using univariate statistics shown in Table 6 (Appendix N) as well as multivariate logistics regression (Figures 7-10) (Appendices R, S, T, U).

Cardiac Surgery.

Cardiac surgery showed statistically significant data in the following categories: OTHBLEED, OPTIME, and RETURNOR. Elective procedures, titled ELECTSURG, trended towards significance ($p < 0.0536$) (OR [95% CI] = 0.763 [0.588=1.004]) (Appendix R). Multivariate statistics for cardiac surgery are displayed in Figure 8. Figure 8 delineates that cardiac surgery cases that experienced a bleeding occurrence requiring transfusion showed 71% greater odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 1.708 [1.297-2.249]) (Appendix R). Blood transfusion occurred at an approximate rate of 50% in cases that did not result in UI, as seen in the univariate statistics. However, blood transfusion and bleeding episodes occurred in 73.3% of cardiac surgery cases that resulted in UI. OPTIME also showed statistical significance ($p < 0.0002$) within the cardiac surgery group (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.001-1.003]). Despite the OR near one, the discrepancy in operative time between cases that resulted in UI and those that did not, was substantial from a clinical standpoint. Cases that resulted in a UI were approximately 40 minutes longer in duration than cases that did not result in a UI. Lastly, RETURNOR showed the strongest correlation to UIs (OR [95% CI] = 5.930 [4.581-7.677]).

Thoracic Surgery.

The data showed statistically significant results ($p < 0.0001$) within the thoracic surgery category for the variables OPTIME, OTHBLEED, RETURNOR, and ELECTSURG (Appendix N). As outlined in Appendix N, a strong positive correlation was seen between UIs and thoracic surgery cases that experienced bleeding occurrences, returns to the operating room, and lengthy operative times (OR [95% CI] = 2.025 [1.680-2.441], 5.741 [4.889-6.743], 1.004 [1.003-1.004])

(Appendix S). As seen in previous surgical specialties, return trips to the operating room were strongly correlated with UI amongst the thoracic surgery population. Although the odds ratio was not far from one in the OPTIME category, the mean operative time difference between UI thoracic cases and non-UI thoracic cases was noteworthy from a clinical standpoint. Thoracic surgeries that resulted in UI were about four hours (238 minutes), while thoracic surgeries that did not result in a UI were roughly two and a half hours (151 minutes). In contrast, elective thoracic surgery (ELECTSURG) demonstrated reduced odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 0.625 [0.505-0.773]) and a negative correlation.

Neurosurgery.

Neurosurgery was associated with multiple statistically significant variables ($p < 0.0001$), including OTHBLEED, RETURNOR, OPTIME, and ELECTSURG (see Appendix N). Positive associations were found between the neurosurgery population requiring UI and bleeding occurrences (OR [95% CI] = 1.477 [1.258-1.735], return to OR (OR [95% CI] = 7.237 [6.422-8.155]), and operative time (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.002-1.003]), shown in Figure 9 (Appendix T). Lastly, the mean operative time shown in Table 6 for neurosurgery cases that resulted in UI was 56 minutes longer than neurosurgery cases that did not require UI (Appendix N).

Head and Neck Surgery.

ENT surgery was linked with two statistically significant variables ($p < 0.0001$): OTHBLEED and RETURNOR (Appendix N). Figure 10 showed the bleeding occurrences requiring transfusions in the ENT patient population which conveyed a strong positive association with UIs (OR [95% CI] = 2.548 [1.642-3.955]) (Appendix U).

Discussion

Multiple NSQIP variables demonstrated statistically significant associations with UIs. The relationship between these variables and UIs bears meaningful consequences when considering perioperative anesthetic management of surgical patients. The average incidence rate of UIs between 2017 to 2019 was found by this DNP project to be 0.62% (Appendix F), which was lower than the 3% incidence rate reported in the existing literature. This discrepancy may be attributed to the criteria measured in this scholarly project compared to that of the more widespread literature on the topic. This scholarly project focused specifically on the surgical factors affecting UIs. In comparison, previous literature takes into account both surgical factors and patient-related factors that contribute to UI. Furthermore, the previous literature cited in this project included surgical specialties such as general and vascular surgery, which were not examined here. However, the lower incidence rate of 0.62% could also indicate that newer data from 2017 to 2019 more accurately depicts the prevalence of UI, alluding to better surgical practices and decreasing UIs overall. Clinically, patients can be screened in advance by both the surgical and anesthesia team in order to prepare for surgery. Preoperative labs can be drawn, and diagnostic studies such as chest x-ray and echocardiograms can be performed to assess patient cardiopulmonary status and function. Optimizing patients before high-risk surgical procedures allows both surgical and anesthesia teams to plan for the safest approach, which maximizes patient safety, as seen by the low incidences of UIs.

This data analysis revealed significant associations between multiple ACS-NSQIP variables and UIs. The most consistently noted variables that showed positive correlations with UI were bleeding occurrences within 72 hours of surgery start time (OTHBLEED), returns to operating room (RETURNOR), and total operative time (OPTIME). These variables were

associated with UIs when analyzed independent of surgical procedure, as well as within the context of the surgical specialties of interest in this study (cardiac, thoracic, neurosurgery, ENT). One of the more interesting relationships uncovered in the data was the negative correlation between MAC/IV Sedation and Spinal anesthesia within the ANESTHES category. Negative correlations were also seen within the neurosurgery and thoracic surgery patient populations when examining whether the surgery was elective vs. emergent (ELECTSURG).

Principle Anesthetic Technique

Discerning the most appropriate anesthetic approach for a given procedure is one of the most critical aspects of perioperative anesthetic case management. The “MAC/IV Sedation” category resulted in significantly decreased odds of exposure to UI during the perioperative period when compared to general anesthesia. When utilizing “MAC/IV Sedation” as the primary anesthetic approach, there were 38-55% decreased odds of experiencing a UI. This is noteworthy as the previous literature suggests that MAC cases that were unexpectedly converted to general anesthesia have been a contributing factor for intraoperative UI. Similarly, the scholarly project demonstrates that UIs were even less likely to occur when spinal anesthesia was the primary anesthetic technique, whereas the literature reports differently (see Appendix K, L, M). The “Spinal” anesthesia category of ACS-NSQIP cases was associated with 66-72% decreased odds of a UI during the years 2017 to 2019. This is important because the previous literature is limited in terms of intraoperative contributors to UIs, and some literature suggests that any non-intubated patient is at risk for intraoperative UI (Parker, 2020). A major question from an anesthesia standpoint is whether non-intubated patients, in cases where the primary anesthetic technique is MAC or spinal anesthesia, have a higher or lower risk of UI during the intraoperative period. If MAC and spinal anesthesia cases are not being converted to general endotracheal anesthesia, as

indicated in this UI data (Appendix K, L, M), then the intraoperative period may not be of primary concern when studying UIs. The data shows that spinal anesthesia and MAC anesthesia are associated with a lower incidence of UI. The implications of this finding (from an anesthesia perspective) beg the question of where and when UIs are occurring. The findings of the DNP scholarly project may help to focus resources and attention around the postoperative setting when assessing for and preventing UIs. However, further research will be necessary to better understand this relationship.

Total Operative Time

Operative time was a recurring variable seen in almost all surgical specialties and across all three years of investigation. On average, cases that resulted in a UI were about an hour longer than cases that did not result in a UI when assessing the aggregate data between 2017 to 2019. Although the odds ratios for these categories did not show a strong relationship (Appendix O, P, Q, R, S, T, U), the mean operative times, as listed in Tables 3-5, show a large discrepancy between cases that did and did not result in UI (Appendix K, L, M). With the exception of ENT surgery, operative time showed a very strong, positive correlation with UI amongst the surgical specialties of interest. From an anesthesia perspective, providers need to be cognizant of the scheduled procedure and the anticipated length the case booked for. If unexpected events occur during a case that prolongs the operative time, anesthesia providers must anticipate the needs of the patient from a respiratory standpoint. Extubation readiness and postoperative planning are paramount for all surgical cases, but especially for those with unexpectedly long operative times.

Return to Operating Room

The RETURNOR category showed the strongest correlation with UI when compared to all other variables of interest portrayed in Figures 4-10 (Appendix O-U). The ORs across all

three years and all four surgical specialties demonstrated an undeniable association between surgical cases that required a return to the operating room and UI. The RETURNOR group showed a 4-fold increase in odds of UI. This could be related to patient comorbidities or surgical acuity. Previous literature from the ACS-NSQIP database has shown that surgical acuity, patient comorbidities, surgical approach, and surgical specialty are significant risk factors for surgical cases requiring an unscheduled return to the operating room (uROR) (Kao et al., 2021). This phenomenon has been relatively well studied, and the need to return to the operating room following a surgical procedure is often indicative of a serious clinical condition (Kao et al., 2021). The strong relationship between RETURNOR and UI seen in this scholarly project could be related to some of the previously identified ACS-NSQIP data on unplanned returns to the operating room (uROR). For example, the risk factor patient comorbidities and surgical acuity outlined in previous literature could potentially influence UIs in the RETURNOR patient population, as many of the surgical specialties examined in this study (cardiac, neurosurgery, thoracic) are commonly associated with multiple patient comorbidities. However, further research must be conducted to discern any potential relationships.

Bleeding Occurrences & Transfusions

Perioperative blood loss is of immense concern to the anesthesia provider. Prompt response to acute bleeding events is vital to patient resuscitation, and this data shows that blood loss can also lead to perioperative UI. Of all the cases that resulted in UI between 2017-2019, roughly one-third of them were associated with a significant bleeding occurrence and blood transfusion. The multivariate analysis indicates increased odds of UI for patients who received perioperative blood transfusions. Patients who received perioperative blood transfusions were at 80-94% increased odds of UI, demonstrating the strong association between bleeding

occurrences and respiratory compromise as a result of hypoperfusion and hypoxia. While transfusing blood increases the oxygen-carrying capacity of blood, thus improving oxygenation of the body, there can also be potentially fatal reactions to blood transfusion, such as Transfusion-Associated Circulatory Overload (TACO) or Transfusion-related Acute Lung Injury (TRALI). TACO is a transfusion reaction that results in pulmonary edema and respiratory distress due to volume or circulatory overload, which can worsen in patients who have other comorbidities, such as congestive heart failure (CHF) (Cho et al., 2022). TRALI is a syndrome that results from noncardiogenic pulmonary edema and potentially acute lung distress syndrome (ARDS), causing hypoxia from blood transfusion (Cho et al., 2022). Both of these pathologies require immediate supportive management to improve oxygenation, which can result in UIs. The life-threatening complications of bleeding occurrences and transfusions further emphasize the importance of continuing the investigation between surgical factors and UIs. Anesthesia providers must be astute and timely with their response to acute perioperative blood loss and understand that this may put the patient at increased risk for respiratory compromise.

Surgical Specialties

The surgical specialties data showed many similarities between all four surgical disciplines (cardiac, neurosurgery, thoracic, ENT). OTHBLEED was seen throughout the data set as a strong indicator of increased odds of UI. This relationship was evident when examined independent of surgical procedure as well as throughout individual surgical specialties. It was most prominently seen in the cardiac surgery and ENT surgery patient populations. Bleeding and blood transfusion showed almost a 75% incidence rate amongst cardiac surgery patients who experienced UI. ENT cases requiring blood transfusions exhibited a 155% increase in odds of UI (see Appendix N). Highly vascular structures associated with ENT surgery, such as the tonsils

and thyroid, in combination with a shared airway, should put anesthesia providers on high alert for perioperative respiratory compromise and possibly UI. In addition, the data shows approximately 50% increased odds of UI for neurosurgery cases that experienced bleeding events. Lastly, thoracic surgery cases where bleeding events transpired were at 100% increased odds of undergoing UI. However, the number of transfusions that cause this association with UI still needs to be investigated. Ultimately, any incidence of blood transfusion should put anesthesia providers on high alert regarding postoperative patient planning in order to avoid UI.

For anesthesia providers, it is necessary to consider the length of surgery and understand the potential for perioperative UI if the duration of the procedure is longer than anticipated. Across all four surgical specialties, longer than anticipated OPTIME was positively correlated with UIs. For example, thoracic surgeries that resulted in UI were about one and a half hours longer than thoracic surgeries that did not result in UI. From an anesthesia perspective, lengthy operative times are often associated with intraoperative complications, and anesthesia providers should therefore consider the potential of UI in their postoperative planning. As expected, RETURNOR showed a dramatic increase in the odds of UI. A profound relationship was found between ENT surgery cases that required a return visit to the operating room and UI (OR [95% CI] = 8.773 [6.436-11.959]) (see Appendix U). When ENT surgery patients experienced a return to the OR, the odds of UI increased by approximately 775%. Cardiac surgery cases that required a return visit to the OR carried approximately six-fold increased odds of requiring a UI. Additionally, neurosurgery cases that required a return trip to the operating room were at roughly 600% increased odds of UI. The data illustrated approximately 475% increased odds of UI within the thoracic surgery group. From a practical standpoint, anesthesia providers can expect

that any surgical patient requiring a return to the OR will most often require reintubation if a secured airway is not already present.

Interestingly, ELECTSURG showed a negative correlation with UIs for neurosurgery and thoracic surgery patients. The elective neurosurgery cases, referred to as ELECTSURG in Figure 9, showed decreased odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 0.536 [0.466-0.617]) (see Appendix T). Patients coming for elective neurosurgery experienced a 46% decrease in the odds of UI. Elective thoracic surgery cases had 38% reduced odds of UI. The data suggest elective procedures may be at a reduced risk of UI, which seems reasonable when comparing elective procedures with urgent or emergent cases. From a clinical standpoint, elective procedures facilitate advanced preoperative planning that allows for patient optimization before surgery. This could include preoperative transfusions to minimize effects of anemia, especially for high-risk surgical specialties mentioned in this scholarly project. Moreover, with optimization, surgeons can better plan the surgical approach to decrease operative time. This may help explain the reduction in UIs seen in elective procedures. Overall, the surgical specialties data elicits convincing, consistent data that affects perioperative planning and anesthetic case management tailored to specific surgical populations. More studies should consider individual surgical specialty populations as a means of focusing analysis and interventions.

Recommendations

Current research on surgical factors and their association with UI is limited but could significantly affect patient safety. Thus, additional research is necessary to better understand these relationships. While the literature suggests that the incidence of UIs amongst the surgical patient population can be as high as 3%, with the mortality rate ranging up to 71%, those studies also assessed patient-related factors, including comorbidities (Hua et al., 2012). Moreover, this

scholarly project's primary aim was to find associations between UIs and surgical factors, which focused on variables deemed connected to UIs from the literature. Although this scholarly DNP project found positive associations with the chosen surgical variables from the ACS-NSQIP database, it does not fully bridge the gap in knowledge between the relationship between UIs and surgical factors. For this reason, recommendations to further investigate other surgical factors associated with UIs are vital to reducing patient morbidity and mortality and alleviating the economic burden placed on healthcare systems.

Increasing knowledge is one of the initial steps needed to further unravel the correlations between surgical factors and UIs. Recommendations for future investigations include performing a comprehensive literature review and expanding secondary data analysis from the ACS-NSQIP database. This could include widening the search criteria to include up to 10 years of data. More surgical specialties could be included to build on the existing data, such as vascular, orthopedic, trauma, obstetrics and gynecology, and general surgery. Furthermore, exploring a connection between number of blood transfusions and UI could prove beneficial. Comparing and contrasting future results with the findings from this scholarly DNP project could help build on the associations established in this study. With more knowledge, interventions can be developed and implemented in the clinical setting to help reduce the incidence of UI, as seen with elective surgeries, and further uncover additional surgical factors that could be contributing to this phenomenon.

Although interventions related to UIs have been trialed, none have been effective in counteracting UIs. The literature suggests that the development of clinical tools such as risk indices could help identify and appropriately plan for patients at increased risk of UI (Hua et al., 2012). With more knowledge of the associations of UIs and surgical factors, a robust clinical

decision-support tool utilizing both surgical factors and patient-related information (age, ASA status, etc.) could help quantify a patient's predisposition to UIs. An effective clinical decision-support tool would utilize and incorporate the data gathered in this study related to operative time, bleeding occurrences and transfusions, and surgical specialty. This would alert anesthesia providers of patients at increased risk of UI and assist in perioperative planning.

Limitations

The results of this study show significant relationships between various surgical variables and UIs. However, they should be understood within the context of the limitations of secondary data analysis. The ACS-NSQIP database only collects data from hospitals participating with ACS-NSQIP and is not representative of every hospital or patient population (American College of Surgeons, 2021a). Moreover, data from ACS-NSQIP does not distinguish between the severity of comorbidities, indications for surgery, or procedure outcomes (Alluri et al., 2016). Other potential confounding variables include surgeon technique/skill level, preexisting airway disease, or postoperative disposition (ambulatory, inpatient, etc.) (American College of Surgeons, 2021b). Of note, the years 2017 to 2019 were intentionally chosen to satisfy a recent secondary data analysis while also excluding data from the recent COVID-19 pandemic. Any data beyond 2019 may have introduced additional bias into the study as fewer elective surgeries were performed during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, the prevalence of a worldwide respiratory virus could have skewed UI data even further. Nonetheless, the large sample size and complete datasets allowed a sufficient cross-sectional analysis of surgical factors affecting UIs.

In conclusion, this DNP scholarly project demonstrated that UIs happen rarely (0.6%), but when considering the disastrous complications of this negative phenomenon, more can be

done to identify and anticipate the needs of patients at risk of UI. Surgical factors that were found to have strong associations with UIs include operative time, returning to OR, and perioperative bleeding. Patients receiving MAC/IV sedation or spinal anesthesia may be at a lower risk of UI, as are elective thoracic and neurosurgery patients. Further research is necessary to better understand these relationships. Performing more comprehensive literature reviews, expanding secondary data analysis, and developing interventions such as clinical support tools (risk indices) could help identify and appropriately plan for patients at increased risk of UI.

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APPENDIX A

Comprehensive Literature Review

Figure 1

Comprehensive literature review

Notes. CINAHL (Cumulated Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature), PubMed (Public Medline), EBSCO (Elton B. Stephens Company)

APPENDIX B

Iowa Model

Figure 2

Iowa model

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APPENDIX C

**Permission to use the Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence
in Health Care****Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics**

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APPENDIX E

CSUF IRB Approval

Date: 11-18-2022

IRB #: HSR-21-22-358
Title: KPSA: Surgical factors associated with unplanned intubations
Creation Date: 5-8-2022
End Date:
Status: Approved
Principal Investigator: Rachel McClanahan
Review Board: Exempt Board
Sponsor:

Study History

Submission Type	Review Type	Decision
Initial	Exempt	Exempt

Key Study Contacts

Member	Role	Contact
Rachel McClanahan	Principal Investigator	rmccclanahan@fullerton.edu
Mario Khong	Primary Contact	mariokhong@csu.fullerton.edu
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Michael Ortegon	Primary Contact	michaelortegon@csu.fullerton.edu

APPENDIX F
KPSC IRB Approval

InterOffice Memorandum

March 4, 2022

To: **Sarah E. Giron, PhD**
100 S. Los Robles Ave. Suite 501,
Pasadena, CA, 91101

Re: Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubations

Dear Dr. Giron,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

APPENDIX G

ACS-NSQIP Surgical Variables

Table 2

ACS-NSQIP Surgical Variables

Variable Name	Variable Label	Variable Options at Entry
ANESTHES	Principle anesthesia technique	Epidural General Local Monitored Anesthesia Care (MAC) / Intravenous (IV) sedation None Other Regional Spinal Unknown
SURGSPEC	Surgical Specialty	Cardiac Surgery Thoracic Surgery Neurosurgery Otolaryngology (ENT)
ELECTSURG	Elective Surgery	Yes; No; Unknown
OPTIME	Total Operation Time	Total operative time in minutes
REINTUB	Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences	Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences
OTHBLEED	Occurrences Bleeding Transfusions	Transfusions Intra/Postop (RBC within the First 72 hrs of Surgery Start Time)
RETURNOR	Return to OR	Unplanned reoperations

APPENDIX H

Query Letter to JCA

This letter is intended to inquire about your interest in publishing a manuscript that examines surgical factors correlated with unplanned intubations (UIs). Our manuscript exhibits a thorough literature review that investigates perioperative surgical factors and their association with unplanned intubations. This manuscript was developed using data from the National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) to find compelling evidence that highlights the importance of this topic as it relates to clinical anesthesia practice. We feel strongly that this research adds to existing nursing literature and upholds your journal's aim of improving clinical anesthesia practice throughout the perioperative period.

Despite advances in healthcare and medical research, various surgical factors continue to put patients at risk for perioperative complications such as unplanned intubations (UIs). Furthermore, postoperative pulmonary complications requiring UI correlate with increased patient morbidity and mortality. As nurse researchers and students in the field of nurse anesthesia, my team and I have discovered a gap in knowledge regarding this subject. Investigation of the risk factors associated with UIs is of paramount importance to not only reduce patient morbidity and mortality, but also to alleviate the economic burden placed on the healthcare system. The goal of this manuscript was to compile information regarding surgical factors and their association with UIs, describe the findings to anesthesia providers (CRNAs and Anesthesiologists), examine the NSQIP dataset, and highlight surgical factors that can serve as a guide for future investigation. The surgical factors with significant impact on perioperative UI include length of surgery, type of surgery (neurological, cardiac, etc.), and intraoperative blood loss. This manuscript is not under review by any other journals, as *The Journal of Clinical Anesthesia* would be our choice publication to disseminate this information.

Our manuscript aims to help fill the gap in knowledge regarding surgical factors correlated with UIs. Our aim aligns with the goals of this journal in contributing new knowledge to clinical practice. Although there have been studies exploring UIs and their relationship to patient outcomes, none have isolated surgical factors as the primary variable for investigation. For this reason, we believe this manuscript is unique and original. Our belief is that this manuscript will appeal to all anesthesia providers and provide significant data that will help reduce perioperative patient morbidity and mortality.

If you are interested in this manuscript and feel it would be of interest, please consider it for publication. We look forward to hearing from you.

Respectfully,

Mario Khong, DNP SRNA and Michael Ortegon, DNP SRNA
DNP Students in Nurse Anesthesia
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia
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APPENDIX I

Permission to Submit Manuscript to JCA

From: Turan, M.D., Alparslan <TURANA@ccl.org>
Sent: Saturday, September 17, 2022 12:13 AM
To: Sarah E Giron <Sarah.E.Giron@kp.org>
Subject: Re: Query Letter for Potential Publication

Caution: This email came from outside Kaiser Permanente. Do not open attachments or click on links if you do not recognize the sender.

Dear Sarah,
Thanks for your email, it's difficult to understand and make a decision on the manuscript with limited information. But for sure its in our scope, please submit it and we will give a fair evaluation.
Regards
Alparslan

From: Sarah E Giron <Sarah.E.Giron@kp.org>
Sent: Friday, September 16, 2022 12:48 PM
To: Turan, M.D., Alparslan <TURANA@ccl.org>
Subject: [EXT] Query Letter for Potential Publication

CAUTION CYBER RISK: This email originated from outside of the organization. Do not click links or open attachments unless you recognize the sender, expected to receive this content and trust that it's safe. If you determine that the email isn't from a trusted source, you can delete the email, submit it via the BlueFish button in Outlook for investigation or forward the email as an attachment to phishhank@kp.org if you don't have the Bluefish button or are on a mobile device.

Dear Professor Turan,
I am writing with a query letter for your journal the *Journal of Clinical Anesthesia*. Please let me know if you have any questions or if you have interest in this type of publication. I look forward to hearing from you and wish you a wonderful weekend.

Be well,

Sarah E. Giron, PhD, CRNA, FAANA
Director
Kaiser Permanente Anesthesia Technology Program
Academic and Clinical Faculty
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia
100 S Los Robles Ave #501, Pasadena, CA 91101
(626) 564-3015 (office)

APPENDIX J

ACS-NSQIP Data from 2017 to 2019

Figure 3

ACS-NSQIP Data from 2017 to 2019

APPENDIX K

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2017

Table 3

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2017

	2017 REINTUB			P-Value
	N	Y	Total	
Overall	1018742	6840	1025582	
ANESTHES, n (%)				<.0001 ²
Epidural	1515 (0.1%)	7 (0.1%)	1522 (0.1%)	
General	904608 (88.8%)	6565 (96.0%)	911173 (88.8%)	
Local	1584 (0.2%)	5 (0.1%)	1589 (0.2%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	50183 (4.9%)	150 (2.2%)	50333 (4.9%)	
Regional	6796 (0.7%)	16 (0.2%)	6812 (0.7%)	
Spinal	54056 (5.3%)	97 (1.4%)	54153 (5.3%)	
SURGSPEC, n (%)				<.0001 ²
Cardiac Surgery	3869 (0.4%)	138 (2.0%)	4007 (0.4%)	
General Surgery	439484 (43.1%)	3685 (53.9%)	443169 (43.2%)	
Gynecology	91804 (9.0%)	99 (1.4%)	91903 (9.0%)	
Interventional Radiologist	102 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	102 (0.0%)	
Neurosurgery	54250 (5.3%)	540 (7.9%)	54790 (5.3%)	
Orthopedics	242643 (23.8%)	651 (9.5%)	243294 (23.7%)	
Otolaryngology (ENT)	27703 (2.7%)	108 (1.6%)	27811 (2.7%)	
Plastics	30853 (3.0%)	41 (0.6%)	30894 (3.0%)	
Thoracic	11913 (1.2%)	369 (5.4%)	12282 (1.2%)	
Urology	60730 (6.0%)	267 (3.9%)	60997 (5.9%)	
Vascular	55391 (5.4%)	942 (13.8%)	56333 (5.5%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	199521 (19.6%)	3702 (54.1%)	203223 (19.8%)	
Unknown	912 (0.1%)	9 (0.1%)	921 (0.1%)	
Yes	818309 (80.3%)	3129 (45.7%)	821438 (80.1%)	
EMERGNCY, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	936573 (91.9%)	5072 (74.2%)	941645 (91.8%)	
Yes	82169 (8.1%)	1768 (25.8%)	83937 (8.2%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²
0	975095 (95.7%)	4572 (66.8%)	979667 (95.5%)	
1	43647 (4.3%)	2268 (33.2%)	45915 (4.5%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No Complication	975095 (95.7%)	4572 (66.8%)	979667 (95.5%)	
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	43647 (4.3%)	2268 (33.2%)	45915 (4.5%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	992811 (97.5%)	4928 (72.0%)	997739 (97.3%)	
Yes	25931 (2.5%)	1912 (28.0%)	27843 (2.7%)	
OPTIME				<.0001 ¹
N	1018620	6839	1025459	
Mean (SD)	109.6 (90.7)	178.7 (137.6)	110.1 (91.3)	

Median (IQR)	84.0 (51.0, 139.0)	137.0 (79.0, 241.0)	85.0 (51.0, 139.0)
Range	0.0, 1434.0	0.0, 1166.0	0.0, 1434.0

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), NOTHBLEED (number of bleeding transfusions occurrences), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), RETURNOR (return to OR), and SURGSPEC (surgical specialty)

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

APPENDIX L

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2018

Table 4

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2018

	2018 REINTUB			P-Value
	N	Y	Total	
Overall	1010719	6367	1017086	
ANESTHES, n (%)				<.0001 ²
Epidural	1075 (0.1%)	4 (0.1%)	1079 (0.1%)	
General	893678 (88.4%)	6079 (95.5%)	899757 (88.5%)	
Local	1315 (0.1%)	7 (0.1%)	1322 (0.1%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	51417 (5.1%)	173 (2.7%)	51590 (5.1%)	
Regional	6208 (0.6%)	22 (0.3%)	6230 (0.6%)	
Spinal	57026 (5.6%)	82 (1.3%)	57108 (5.6%)	
SURGSPEC, n (%)				<.0001 ²
Cardiac Surgery	3921 (0.4%)	129 (2.0%)	4050 (0.4%)	
General Surgery	428147 (42.4%)	3413 (53.6%)	431560 (42.4%)	
Gynecology	98556 (9.8%)	111 (1.7%)	98667 (9.7%)	
Interventional Radiologist	156 (0.0%)	2 (0.0%)	158 (0.0%)	
Neurosurgery	53000 (5.2%)	521 (8.2%)	53521 (5.3%)	
Orthopedics	249424 (24.7%)	696 (10.9%)	250120 (24.6%)	
Otolaryngology (ENT)	26438 (2.6%)	96 (1.5%)	26534 (2.6%)	
Plastics	31454 (3.1%)	46 (0.7%)	31500 (3.1%)	
Thoracic	12118 (1.2%)	332 (5.2%)	12450 (1.2%)	
Urology	59656 (5.9%)	220 (3.5%)	59876 (5.9%)	
Vascular	47849 (4.7%)	801 (12.6%)	48650 (4.8%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	204498 (20.2%)	3576 (56.2%)	208074 (20.5%)	
Unknown	1000 (0.1%)	4 (0.1%)	1004 (0.1%)	
Yes	805221 (79.7%)	2787 (43.8%)	808008 (79.4%)	
EMERGNCY, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	925220 (91.5%)	4656 (73.1%)	929876 (91.4%)	
Yes	85499 (8.5%)	1711 (26.9%)	87210 (8.6%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²
0	969903 (96.0%)	4363 (68.5%)	974266 (95.8%)	
1	40816 (4.0%)	2004 (31.5%)	42820 (4.2%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No Complication	969903 (96.0%)	4363 (68.5%)	974266 (95.8%)	
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	40816 (4.0%)	2004 (31.5%)	42820 (4.2%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.0001 ²
No	985404 (97.5%)	4514 (70.9%)	989918 (97.3%)	
Yes	25315 (2.5%)	1853 (29.1%)	27168 (2.7%)	
OPTIME				<.0001 ¹
N	1010560	6366	1016926	

Mean (SD)	110.8 (91.0)	176.7 (139.3)	111.2 (91.6)
Median (IQR)	85.0 (51.0, 140.0)	135.0 (76.0, 237.0)	85.0 (52.0, 141.0)
Range	0.0, 1440.0	2.0, 1357.0	0.0, 1440.0

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC

(monitored anesthesia care), NOTHBLEED (number of bleeding transfusions occurrences),

OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), RETURNOR

(return to OR), and SURGSPEC (surgical specialty)

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

APPENDIX M

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2019

Table 5

Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors in 2019

	2019 REINTUB			P-Value
	N	Y	Total	
	1039160	5944	1045104	
ANESTHES, n (%)				<.00012
Epidural	4311 (0.4%)	14 (0.2%)	4325 (0.4%)	
General	901903 (86.8%)	5708 (96.0%)	907611 (86.8%)	
Local	1030 (0.1%)	2 (0.0%)	1032 (0.1%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	56826 (5.5%)	113 (1.9%)	56939 (5.4%)	
Regional	7053 (0.7%)	16 (0.3%)	7069 (0.7%)	
Spinal	68037 (6.5%)	91 (1.5%)	68128 (6.5%)	
SURGSPEC, n (%)				<.00012
Cardiac Surgery	4119 (0.4%)	115 (1.9%)	4234 (0.4%)	
General Surgery	424961 (40.9%)	3234 (54.4%)	428195 (41.0%)	
Gynecology	107847 (10.4%)	102 (1.7%)	107949 (10.3%)	
Interventional Radiologist	60 (0.0%)	2 (0.0%)	62 (0.0%)	
Neurosurgery	56267 (5.4%)	550 (9.3%)	56817 (5.4%)	
Orthopedics	262156 (25.2%)	619 (10.4%)	262775 (25.1%)	
Otolaryngology (ENT)	24495 (2.4%)	80 (1.3%)	24575 (2.4%)	
Plastics	31111 (3.0%)	34 (0.6%)	31145 (3.0%)	
Thoracic	11850 (1.1%)	327 (5.5%)	12177 (1.2%)	
Urology	63604 (6.1%)	220 (3.7%)	63824 (6.1%)	
Vascular	41415 (4.0%)	647 (10.9%)	42062 (4.0%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.00012
No	217814 (21.0%)	3317 (55.8%)	221131 (21.2%)	
Unknown	1331 (0.1%)	5 (0.1%)	1336 (0.1%)	
Yes	820015 (78.9%)	2622 (44.1%)	822637 (78.7%)	
EMERGNCY, n (%)				<.00012
No	945964 (91.0%)	4255 (71.6%)	950219 (90.9%)	
Yes	93196 (9.0%)	1689 (28.4%)	94885 (9.1%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.00012
0	998618 (96.1%)	4122 (69.3%)	1002740 (95.9%)	
1	40542 (3.9%)	1822 (30.7%)	42364 (4.1%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.00012
No Complication	998618 (96.1%)	4122 (69.3%)	1002740 (95.9%)	
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	40542 (3.9%)	1822 (30.7%)	42364 (4.1%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.00012
No	1014801 (97.7%)	4213 (70.9%)	1019014 (97.5%)	
Yes	24359 (2.3%)	1731 (29.1%)	26090 (2.5%)	
OPTIME				<.00011
N	1039027	5942	1044969	

Mean (SD)	111.1 (91.1)	185.8 (141.2)	111.6 (91.6)
Median (IQR)	85.0 (52.0, 140.0)	144.0 (83.0, 248.0)	86.0 (52.0, 141.0)
Range	0.0, 1440.0	0.0, 1107.0	0.0, 1440.0

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC

(monitored anesthesia care), NOTHBLEED (number of bleeding transfusions occurrences),

OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), RETURNOR

(return to OR), and SURGSPEC (surgical specialty)

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

APPENDIX N

Study Characteristics of Surgical Specialties

Table 6

Study Characteristics by Surgical Specialties

	Cardiac REINTUB				Thoracic REINTUB				Neurosurgery REINTUB				ENT REINTUB			
	N (N=11909)	Y (N=382)	Total (N=12291)	P-value	N (N=35877)	Y (N=1028)	Total (N=36905)	P-value	N (N=163516)	Y (N=1611)	Total (N=165127)	P-value	N (N=78635)	Y (N=284)	Total (N=78919)	P-value
Overall																
ANESTHES, n (%)				0.1311 ²				0.9745 ²				0.5266 ²				0.0002 ²
Epidural	3 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (0.0%)		76 (0.2%)	3 (0.3%)	79 (0.2%)		29 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	29 (0.0%)		9 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (0.0%)	
General	11539 (96.9%)	380 (99.5%)	11919 (97.0%)		35643 (99.3%)	1020 (99.2%)	36663 (99.3%)		161225 (98.6%)	1596 (99.1%)	162821 (98.6%)		77603 (98.7%)	279 (98.2%)	77882 (98.7%)	
Local	7 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (0.1%)		9 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (0.0%)		97 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	97 (0.1%)		62 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	62 (0.1%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	304 (2.6%)	2 (0.5%)	306 (2.5%)		116 (0.3%)	4 (0.4%)	120 (0.3%)		1784 (1.1%)	14 (0.9%)	1798 (1.1%)		894 (1.1%)	4 (1.4%)	898 (1.1%)	
Regional	5 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (0.0%)		4 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (0.0%)		134 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	134 (0.1%)		10 (0.0%)	1 (0.4%)	11 (0.0%)	
Spinal	51 (0.4%)	0 (0.0%)	51 (0.4%)		29 (0.1%)	1 (0.1%)	30 (0.1%)		247 (0.2%)	1 (0.1%)	248 (0.2%)		57 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	57 (0.1%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	5187 (43.6%)	214 (56.0%)	5401 (43.9%)		5107 (14.2%)	274 (26.7%)	5381 (14.6%)		29538 (18.1%)	956 (59.3%)	30494 (18.5%)		2868 (3.6%)	39 (13.7%)	2907 (3.7%)	
Unknown	7 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (0.1%)		21 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	21 (0.1%)		50 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	50 (0.0%)		149 (0.2%)	1 (0.4%)	150 (0.2%)	
Yes	6715 (56.4%)	168 (44.0%)	6883 (56.0%)		30749 (85.7%)	754 (73.3%)	31503 (85.4%)		133928 (81.9%)	655 (40.7%)	134583 (81.5%)		75618 (96.2%)	244 (85.9%)	75862 (96.1%)	
EMERGENCY, n (%)				0.0023 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	10909 (91.6%)	333 (87.2%)	11242 (91.5%)		34891 (97.3%)	978 (95.1%)	35869 (97.2%)		156066 (95.4%)	1201 (74.5%)	157267 (95.2%)		77781 (98.9%)	269 (94.7%)	78050 (98.9%)	
Yes	1000 (8.4%)	49 (12.8%)	1049 (8.5%)		986 (2.7%)	50 (4.9%)	1036 (2.8%)		7450 (4.6%)	410 (25.5%)	7860 (4.8%)		854 (1.1%)	15 (5.3%)	869 (1.1%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
0	6105 (51.3%)	102 (26.7%)	6207 (50.5%)		34094 (95.0%)	767 (74.6%)	34861 (94.5%)		156955 (96.0%)	1318 (81.8%)	158273 (95.8%)		77749 (98.9%)	233 (82.0%)	77982 (98.8%)	
1	5804 (48.7%)	280 (73.3%)	6084 (49.5%)		1783 (5.0%)	261 (25.4%)	2044 (5.5%)		6561 (4.0%)	293 (18.2%)	6854 (4.2%)		886 (1.1%)	51 (18.0%)	937 (1.2%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	3869 (32.5%)	61 (16.0%)	3930 (32.0%)		34094 (95.0%)	767 (74.6%)	34861 (94.5%)		156955 (96.0%)	1318 (81.8%)	158273 (95.8%)		77749 (98.9%)	233 (82.0%)	77982 (98.8%)	
No Complication	2236 (18.8%)	41 (10.7%)	2277 (18.5%)													
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	5804 (48.7%)	280 (73.3%)	6084 (49.5%)		1783 (5.0%)	261 (25.4%)	2044 (5.5%)		6561 (4.0%)	293 (18.2%)	6854 (4.2%)		886 (1.1%)	51 (18.0%)	937 (1.2%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	11251 (94.5%)	263 (68.8%)	11514 (93.7%)		34446 (96.0%)	702 (68.3%)	35148 (95.2%)		158189 (96.7%)	1077 (66.9%)	159266 (96.5%)		76533 (97.3%)	165 (58.1%)	76698 (97.2%)	
Yes	658 (5.5%)	119 (31.2%)	777 (6.3%)		1431 (4.0%)	326 (31.7%)	1757 (4.8%)		5327 (3.3%)	534 (33.1%)	5861 (3.5%)		2102 (2.7%)	119 (41.9%)	2221 (2.8%)	
OPTIME				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹
N	11905	382	12287		35875	1028	36903		163503	1611	165114		78630	283	78913	
Mean (SD)	233.7 (109.3)	278.2 (116.4)	255.1 (109.8)		151.1 (107.3)	238.4 (161.8)	153.5 (110.1)		156.1 (104.5)	212.2 (142.7)	156.6 (105.0)		120.5 (130.1)	292.4 (241.6)	121.1 (131.0)	
Median (IQR)	227.0 (165.0, 293.0)	269.0 (212.0, 334.0)	229.0 (166.0, 294.0)		126.0 (73.0, 198.0)	203.0 (110.0, 334.5)	127.0 (73.0, 201.0)		129.0 (84.0, 199.0)	173.0 (110.0, 273.0)	130.0 (84.0, 200.0)		84.0 (39.0, 149.0)	217.0 (105.0, 451.0)	84.0 (39.0, 150.0)	
Range	2.0, 1214.0	25.0, 694.0	2.0, 1214.0		0.0, 1144.0	9.0, 972.0	0.0, 1144.0		0.0, 1300.0	10.0, 894.0	0.0, 1300.0		0.0, 1440.0	6.0, 1357.0	0.0, 1440.0	

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), NOTHBLEED (number of bleeding transfusions occurrences), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), RETURNOR (return to OR), and SURGSPEC (surgical specialty)

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

APPENDIX O

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2017

Figure 4

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2017

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Type 3 Wald p-value;

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX P

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2018

Figure 5

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2018

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Type 3 Wald p-value;

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX Q

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2019

Figure 6

Multivariate Logistic Regression for 2019

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Type 3 Wald p-value;

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), IV (intravenous), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX R

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Cardiac

Figure 7

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Cardiac

¹Covariate Wald p-value;

Note. ELECTSURG (elective surgery), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX S

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Thoracic

Figure 8

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Thoracic

¹Covariate Wald p-value;

Note. ELECTSURG (elective surgery), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX T

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Neurosurgery

Figure 9

Multivariate Logistic Regression for Neurosurgery

¹Covariate Wald p-value;

Note. ELECTSURG (elective surgery), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX U

Multivariate Logistic Regression for ENT

Figure 10

Multivariate Logistic Regression for ENT

¹Covariate Wald p-value;

Note. ANESTHES (anesthesia type), ELECTSURG (elective surgery), MAC (monitored anesthesia care), IV (intravenous), OPTIME (operation time), OTHBLEED (occurrence of bleeding transfusions), and RETURNOR (return to OR)

APPENDIX V

Manuscript to JCA: Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubation

Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubations

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A B S T R A C T

Importance: Although the reported incidence of unplanned intubations (UIs) is low (3%), the associated morbidity and mortality is 50%. For this reason, investigation of surgical factors affecting UIs is paramount. Recent literature suggests the surgical factors affecting UIs include length of surgery, type of surgery, perioperative blood loss, hemodynamic instability, and airway compromise, but studies are conflicting.

Objective: Conduct a retrospective data analysis of the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS-NSQIP) database to examine correlation between surgical factors and UIs.

Design: Retrospective cohort study

Setting: Outpatient and inpatient surgery

Patients: 3,087,654 patients who underwent surgery between 2017 and 2019 per the ACS-NSQIP database.

Interventions: Primary exposure variables: anesthetic technique (epidural, general, MAC/IV sedation, regional, spinal, local), type of surgery (cardiac, thoracic, ENT, neurosurgery), operative time (OPTIME), blood loss/transfusions (OTHBLEED), elective (ELECTSURG) and emergent surgery (EMERGNCY) and return to operating room (RETURNOR).

Measurements: Primary outcome measure: Unplanned intubations (REINTUB). Logistic regression was used to calculate odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

Main results: The incidence rate of UIs was found to be 0.62% in all surgical populations across all three years. OPTIME, OTHBLEED, and RETURNOR demonstrated significant correlations when examined individually and within the context of specific surgical specialties ($p < 0.0001$). ELECTSURG and EMERGNCY cases also indicate significant associations with UIs when examined overall ($p < 0.0001$) but not every surgical specialty.

Conclusions: UIs are significantly correlated with long operative times, postoperative return to the operating room, and perioperative bleeding. Specific surgical specialties also have notable impact on the incidence of UI. These variables should be incorporated into anesthesia perioperative planning and case management to help prevent morbidity and mortality associated with UIs and improve patient safety.

Keywords: unplanned intubations (UIs), unintended intubations (UIs), American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS-NSQIP), surgical factors

1. Introduction

Despite advances in healthcare, various surgical factors continue to be associated with unplanned intubation (UI) and adverse patient outcomes throughout the perioperative period. Surgical factors contribute to 16% of postoperative complications resulting in pulmonary compromise [1]. Furthermore, postoperative pulmonary complications requiring UI have been associated with a 4-fold increase in patient morbidity and mortality in the 30 days following surgery [1,2,3,4]. Existing research shows that UIs occur with a frequency of 3% in the surgical population; however, the associated mortality rate for the UI patient population ranges from 31-71% [5]. Although the documented occurrence of UIs is relatively low, the mortality rate of patients requiring UI is unconscionably high. For this reason, further investigation of the risk factors associated with UIs is of paramount importance to reduce patient morbidity and mortality.

In addition to increased patient morbidity and mortality, there is a 9- to 10-fold increase in hospital costs associated with perioperative UIs [2,3,4]. It is estimated that UIs and their sequelae cost the United States healthcare system an estimated \$1.96 billion dollars annually [1,3]. Previous studies have attempted to create tools such as risk calculators or indices to help identify patients at risk for UI with many of these studies focusing on patient comorbidities or demographic information as predictors of UI. Although these studies ascertain important patient-related data thought to influence UIs, the entire surgical experience must be examined to provide a complete picture. Therefore, to alleviate the economic burden placed on healthcare systems and further explore this rare but deadly phenomenon, specific surgical considerations affecting UIs should be thoroughly investigated.

Surgical factors related to UIs are largely under-investigated, demonstrating a dearth of surgical patient safety information. Current literature suggests that surgical factors affecting UIs may include the length of surgery, type of surgery, and perioperative blood loss but there is a clear knowledge gap regarding surgical factors and their effect on UIs. Additionally, many of the existing studies are outdated and fail to utilize large sample sizes inclusive of diverse surgical patient populations. This study utilized the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS-NSQIP) national database to examine the surgical variables correlated with UIs in patients that underwent surgery from 2017 to 2019. Variables of interest included length of surgery, blood loss and transfusions, emergent or elective nature of the surgery, need for a return to the operating room (OR) or unplanned operation, type of anesthesia required by the surgery and type of surgery (cardiothoracic, neurosurgery, and head and neck [ENT]). Through correlative investigation, this study aimed to explore those surgical factors that could be mitigated to help reduce the relatively high patient morbidity and mortality associated with UIs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Data registry

In this retrospective cohort study, Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) and California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) IRB approvals were obtained prior to data collection. All data were extracted from the ASC-NSQIP database, which is a robust, globally recognized dataset comprised of deidentified patient

information. The data was collected from ACS-NSQIP and stored on secure servers within the Kaiser Permanente Health System. All data were entered into spreadsheets on secure and encrypted networks under the guidelines of the Kaiser Permanente Quality Safety and Regulatory Oversight Department (KP-QSROD). Only aggregate results, no individual patient-level data were handled during the entirety of the project.

2.2 Study population and outcome measures

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the association of UI with length of surgery, blood loss and transfusions, emergent or elective nature of the surgery, need for a return to the operating room (OR) or reoperation, type of anesthesia required by the surgery and type of surgery (cardiothoracic, neurosurgery, and ENT) (Table 1). All the surgical factors extracted were correlated with cases that noted at least one UI from the ACS-NSQIP database during the years 2017 to 2019. Demographic variables such as age, gender, ethnicity, and other health history information were not the primary focus of data analysis and thus not included for descriptive or correlative analysis.

Table 1
ACS-NSQIP Surgical Variables

Variable Name	Variable Label	Variable Options at Entry
ANESTHES	Principle anesthesia technique	Epidural
		General
		Local
		Monitored Anesthesia Care (MAC) / Intravenous (IV) sedation
		None
		Other
		Regional
		Spinal
		Unknown
SURSPEC	Surgical Specialty	Cardiac Surgery
		Thoracic Surgery
		Neurosurgery
		Otolaryngology (ENT)
ELECTSURG	Elective Surgery	Yes; No; Unknown
OPTIME	Total operation time	Total operative time in minutes
REINTUB	Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences	Number of Unplanned Intubation Occurrences
OTHBLEED	Occurrences Bleeding Transfusions	Transfusions Intra/Postop (RBC within the Frist 72 hrs of Surgery Start time)
RETURNOR	Return to OR	Unplanned reoperations

2.3 Definition of primary exposure variable

Unintended intubation was the primary outcome variable during this retrospective analysis. For the purpose of this study, the definition chosen for UI was adopted from ACS-NSQIP and is considered “an unanticipated event that requires placement of an advanced airway, such as an endotracheal tube or laryngeal mask airway (LMA), occurring during the intraoperative period or within 30 days following a surgical procedure” [2]. Included in this definition were reintubations due to cardiac arrest, extubations requiring reintubations, or intubation during the postoperative period for hemodynamic concerns. Excluded from this definition were patients with a chronic tracheostomy who require intermittent ventilator support.

2.4. Data collected

The principal aim of this research endeavor was to examine the relationship between the surgical factors identified and UIs. All extracted surgical cases came from ACS-NSQIP from 2017 to 2019 with oversight by KP-QSROD. A total of 3,087,654 patients who underwent surgery between 2017 and 2019 were included for analysis.

2.5 Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to describe sample characteristics and categorical variables as they relate to the variables listed in Table 1. The frequency of UIs was determined by examining the NSQIP dataset for the rate of UIs (REINTUB) across the entire surgical population, across all years for a cumulative average incidence rate, and individual years for a yearly incidence rate. Data were compared between those patients who did and did not get reintubated for each year. The rate of UI among the different surgical variables was compared via univariate and multivariate logistic regression. For univariate analysis, characteristics of patients were reported as percentages for categorical variables and median, interquartile (IQR) and range were used for continuous variables. The Chi-Square tests were used to test for categorical differences in reintubated groups. Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to calculate differences on continuous variables. Multivariate logistic regression was performed, and odds ratios and confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to detect the factors associated with the probability of reintubation for each year. Variables with the significant result and clinically meaningful differences between the reintubated groups from the univariate analysis were used in the predictive model. Forest plots were produced to display the results graphically. Wald test was used to calculate p-values for the odds ratios. The same univariate and multivariate analyses were further performed and stratified by surgery types, including of Cardiac, Thoracic, Neuro, and ENT surgeries with 2017 to 2019 data combined. All analyses were two-sided and performed using SAS EG 8.2 (Cary, NC). P values of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

There were 3,087,654 patients who underwent surgery from the ACS-NSQIP database from 2017 to 2019. Among the total sample, 3,068,503 cases did not result in UIs and 19,151 (0.62%) were associated with UIs. In 2017, there were 1,025,582 total cases recorded in the ACS-NSQIP database where 6,840 (0.66%) resulted in an UI. The following years, 2018 (0.63%) and 2019 (0.57%) showed similar rates of UI within similar sample sizes. Table 2 lists the patient and outcome characteristics of each ACS-NSQIP studied variable with Figures 1-2 highlighting each variable of interest in forest plots.

3.1 Principle Anesthetic Technique

The principle anesthetic technique (ANESTHES) category was divided into groups to reflect the primary anesthetic approach for each surgical case including MAC (monitored anesthesia care) and IV (intravenous) sedation, spinal, epidural, local, and regional anesthesia. The “MAC/IV Sedation” category showed a statistically significant relationship with UIs ($p < 0.0001$) (Table 2). This data was consistent over all three years (OR [95% CI] = 0.551 [0.465-0.653], 0.616 [0.524-0.725], 0.474 [0.388-0.579] for years 2017 to 2019 respectively) with odds

ratios less than one, indicating a negative correlation to UIs (Fig. 1). When examining “Spinal” anesthesia as the primary anesthetic approach, all three years showed a statistically significant relationship with UIs ($p < 0.0001$). The ORs for this group demonstrated a negative correlation between “Spinal” anesthesia and UIs as well (OR [95% CI] = 0.313 [0.252-0.390], 0.281 [0.220-0.360], 0.341 [0.270-0.430]) as seen in Figure 1.

3.2 Total Operative Time

The ACS-NSQIP variable for total operative time (OPTIME) showed statistical significance across all three years of interest ($p < 0.0001$). Total operative time was measured in minutes, comparing the total operative time for cases that did or did not result in UI. The multivariate statistics for this category showed odds ratios very close to 1 across all three years (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.002-1.003], 1.003 [1.002-1.003], 1.003 [1.002-1.003]) shown in Figure 1. Although the odds ratios do not show a strong relationship, the univariate analysis (Table 2) quantifies the mean operative time for all cases for each respective year. In 2017, mean operative time for non-reintubated patients was 109.6 minutes compared with 178.7 minutes for those that did require reintubation. A similar relationship was present between these two groups during 2018 (110.8 minutes versus 176.6 minutes) and 2019 (111.1 min and 185.8 minutes). On average, cases that resulted in an UI were approximately one hour longer than cases that did not.

3.3 Return to Operating Room

Surgical cases that resulted in a return to the operating room (RETURNOR) were very strongly correlated with UIs ($p < 0.0001$). The multivariate logistic regression for this category showed strong positive correlation with UI (OR [95% CI] = 5.166 [4.856-5.496], 5.644 [5.297-6.014], 5.860 [5.484-6.261]) as seen in Figure 1. This pattern was seen consistently in the data from 2017 to 2019.

3.4 Bleeding Occurrences and Transfusions

Bleeding occurrences requiring transfusions (OTHBLEED), was defined as transfusions of red blood cells (RBCs) within the first 72 hours of surgery start time. Tables 2 demonstrate statistical significance in this category across all three years of interest ($p < 0.0001$). A strong positive correlation was borne out in the evidence as displayed in Figure 1 (OR [95% CI] = 1.940 [1.816-2.072], 1.808 [1.688-1.937], 1.810 [1.683-1.946]).

3.5 Emergent and Elective Cases

Elective surgeries (ELECTSURG) were negatively correlated with UIs ($p < 0.0001$) across all three years of data collection. As seen in Table 2, the univariate statistics show that 43-48% of all reintubated cases were elective procedures. In contrast, 79-80% of non-reintubated cases were elective procedures. In addition, the multivariate statistics in Figure 1 exhibit a negative correlation between procedures that were confirmed as elective and UIs (OR [95% CI] = 0.760 [0.708-0.817], 0.743 [0.688-0.802], 0.741 [0.685-0.803]).

3.6 Surgical Specialties

3.6.1 Cardiac Surgery

Cardiac surgery showed statistically significant data in the following categories: OTHBLEED, OPTIME, and RETURNOR. Elective procedures, titled ELECTSURG, trended towards significance ($p < 0.0536$) (Table 3) (OR [95% CI] = 0.763 [0.588-1.004]) (Fig. 2). Multivariate logistic regression for cardiac surgery delineates that cardiac surgery cases that experienced a bleeding occurrence requiring transfusion showed 71% greater odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 1.708 [1.297-2.249]) (Fig. 2). Blood transfusion occurred at an approximate rate of 50% in cases that did not result in UI, as seen in the univariate statistics. However, blood transfusion and bleeding episodes occurred in 73.3% of cardiac surgery cases that resulted in UI. OPTIME also showed statistical significance ($p < 0.0002$) within the cardiac surgery group (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.001-1.003]). Despite an odds ratio near one, the discrepancy in operative time between cases that resulted in UI and those that did not, was substantial from a clinical standpoint. Cases that resulted in an UI were approximately 40 minutes longer in duration than cases that did not result in an UI. Lastly, RETURNOR showed the strongest correlation to UIs (OR [95% CI] = 5.930 [4.581-7.677]) (Fig. 2).

3.6.2 Thoracic Surgery

The data showed statistically significant results ($p < 0.0001$) within the thoracic surgery category for the variables OPTIME, OTHBLEED, RETURNOR, and ELECTSURG (Table 3). A strong positive correlation was seen between UIs and thoracic surgery cases that experienced bleeding occurrences, returns to the operating room, and lengthy operative times (OR [95% CI] = 2.025 [1.680-2.441], 5.741 [4.889-6.743], 1.004 [1.003-1.004]) (Fig. 2). As seen in previous surgical specialties, return trips to the operating room were strongly correlated with UI amongst the thoracic surgery population. Although the odds ratio was not far from one in the OPTIME category, the mean operative time difference between UI thoracic cases and non-UI thoracic cases was noteworthy from a clinical standpoint. Thoracic surgeries that resulted in UI were about four hours (238 minutes) while thoracic surgeries that did not result in an UI were roughly two and a half hours (151 minutes). In contrast, elective thoracic surgery (ELECTSURG) demonstrated a negative correlation with reduced odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 0.625 [0.505-0.773]) (Fig. 2).

3.6.3 Neurosurgery

Neurosurgery was associated with multiple statistically significant variables ($p < 0.0001$) including OTHBLEED, RETURNOR, OPTIME, and ELECTSURG (Table 3). Positive associations were found between the neurosurgery population requiring UI and bleeding occurrences (OR [95% CI] = 1.477 [1.258-1.735], return to OR (OR [95% CI] = 7.237 [6.422-8.155]), and operative time (OR [95% CI] = 1.002 [1.002-1.003]) (Fig. 2). Lastly, the mean operative time shown in Table 3 for neurosurgery cases that resulted in UI were 56 minutes longer than neurosurgery cases that did not require UI.

3.6.4 ENT

ENT surgery was linked with two statistically significant variables ($p < 0.0001$): OTHBLEED and RETURNOR (Table 3). Figure 2 showed the bleeding occurrences requiring transfusions in the ENT patient population which conveyed a strong positive association with UIs (OR [95% CI] = 2.548 [1.642-3.955]).

Table 2
Study Characteristics by Surgical Factors from 2017 to 2019

	2017 REINTUB				2018 REINTUB				2019 REINTUB			
	N (N=1018742)	Y (N=6840)	Total (N=1025582)	P-value	N (N=1010719)	Y (N=6367)	Total (N=1017086)	P-value	N (N=1039160)	Y (N=5944)	Total (N=1045104)	P-value
ANESTHES, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
Epidural	1515 (0.1%)	7 (0.1%)	1522 (0.1%)		1075 (0.1%)	4 (0.1%)	1079 (0.1%)		4311 (0.4%)	14 (0.2%)	4325 (0.4%)	
General	904608 (88.8%)	6565 (96.0%)	911173 (88.8%)		893678 (88.4%)	6079 (95.5%)	899757 (88.5%)		901903 (86.8%)	5708 (96.0%)	907611 (86.8%)	
Local	1584 (0.2%)	5 (0.1%)	1589 (0.2%)		1315 (0.1%)	7 (0.1%)	1322 (0.1%)		1030 (0.1%)	2 (0.0%)	1032 (0.1%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	50183 (4.9%)	150 (2.2%)	50333 (4.9%)		51417 (5.1%)	173 (2.7%)	51590 (5.1%)		56826 (5.5%)	113 (1.9%)	56939 (5.4%)	
Regional	6796 (0.7%)	16 (0.2%)	6812 (0.7%)		6208 (0.6%)	22 (0.3%)	6230 (0.6%)		7053 (0.7%)	16 (0.3%)	7069 (0.7%)	
Spinal	54056 (5.3%)	97 (1.4%)	54153 (5.3%)		57026 (5.6%)	82 (1.3%)	57108 (5.6%)		68037 (6.5%)	91 (1.5%)	68128 (6.5%)	
SURGSPEC, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
Cardiac Surgery	3869 (0.4%)	138 (2.0%)	4007 (0.4%)		3921 (0.4%)	129 (2.0%)	4050 (0.4%)		4119 (0.4%)	115 (1.9%)	4234 (0.4%)	
General Surgery	439484 (43.1%)	3685 (53.9%)	443169 (43.2%)		428147 (42.4%)	3413 (53.6%)	431560 (42.4%)		424961 (40.9%)	3234 (54.4%)	428195 (41.0%)	
Gynecology	91804 (9.0%)	99 (1.4%)	91903 (9.0%)		98556 (9.8%)	111 (1.7%)	98667 (9.7%)		107847 (10.4%)	102 (1.7%)	107949 (10.3%)	
Interventional Radiologist	102 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	102 (0.0%)		156 (0.0%)	2 (0.0%)	158 (0.0%)		60 (0.0%)	2 (0.0%)	62 (0.0%)	
Neurosurgery	54250 (5.3%)	540 (7.9%)	54790 (5.3%)		53000 (5.2%)	521 (8.2%)	53521 (5.3%)		56267 (5.4%)	550 (9.3%)	56817 (5.4%)	
Orthopedics	242643 (23.8%)	651 (9.5%)	243294 (23.7%)		249424 (24.7%)	696 (10.9%)	250120 (24.6%)		262156 (25.2%)	619 (10.4%)	262775 (25.1%)	
Otolaryngology (ENT)	27703 (2.7%)	108 (1.6%)	27811 (2.7%)		26438 (2.6%)	96 (1.5%)	26534 (2.6%)		24495 (2.4%)	80 (1.3%)	24575 (2.4%)	
Plastics	30853 (3.0%)	41 (0.6%)	30894 (3.0%)		31454 (3.1%)	46 (0.7%)	31500 (3.1%)		31111 (3.0%)	34 (0.6%)	31145 (3.0%)	
Thoracic	11913 (1.2%)	369 (5.4%)	12282 (1.2%)		12118 (1.2%)	332 (5.2%)	12450 (1.2%)		11850 (1.1%)	327 (5.5%)	12177 (1.2%)	
Urology	60730 (6.0%)	267 (3.9%)	60997 (5.9%)		59656 (5.9%)	220 (3.5%)	59876 (5.9%)		63604 (6.1%)	220 (3.7%)	63824 (6.1%)	
Vascular	55391 (5.4%)	942 (13.8%)	56333 (5.5%)		47849 (4.7%)	801 (12.6%)	48650 (4.8%)		41415 (4.0%)	647 (10.9%)	42062 (4.0%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	199521 (19.6%)	3702 (54.1%)	203223 (19.8%)		204498 (20.2%)	3576 (56.2%)	208074 (20.5%)		217814 (21.0%)	3317 (55.8%)	221131 (21.2%)	
Unknown	912 (0.1%)	9 (0.1%)	921 (0.1%)		1000 (0.1%)	4 (0.1%)	1004 (0.1%)		1331 (0.1%)	5 (0.1%)	1336 (0.1%)	
Yes	818309 (80.3%)	3129 (45.7%)	821438 (80.1%)		805221 (79.7%)	2787 (43.8%)	808008 (79.4%)		820015 (78.9%)	2622 (44.1%)	822637 (78.7%)	
EMERGENCY, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	936573 (91.9%)	5072 (74.2%)	941645 (91.8%)		925220 (91.5%)	4656 (73.1%)	929876 (91.4%)		945964 (91.0%)	4255 (71.6%)	950219 (90.9%)	
Yes	82169 (8.1%)	1768 (25.8%)	83937 (8.2%)		85499 (8.5%)	1711 (26.9%)	87210 (8.6%)		93196 (9.0%)	1689 (28.4%)	94885 (9.1%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
0	975095 (95.7%)	4572 (66.8%)	979667 (95.5%)		969903 (96.0%)	4363 (68.5%)	974266 (95.8%)		998618 (96.1%)	4122 (69.3%)	1002740 (95.9%)	
1	43647 (4.3%)	2268 (33.2%)	45915 (4.5%)		40816 (4.0%)	2004 (31.5%)	42820 (4.2%)		40542 (3.9%)	1822 (30.7%)	42364 (4.1%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No Complication	975095 (95.7%)	4572 (66.8%)	979667 (95.5%)		969903 (96.0%)	4363 (68.5%)	974266 (95.8%)		998618 (96.1%)	4122 (69.3%)	1002740 (95.9%)	
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	43647 (4.3%)	2268 (33.2%)	45915 (4.5%)		40816 (4.0%)	2004 (31.5%)	42820 (4.2%)		40542 (3.9%)	1822 (30.7%)	42364 (4.1%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	992811 (97.5%)	4928 (72.0%)	997739 (97.3%)		985404 (97.5%)	4514 (70.9%)	989918 (97.3%)		1014801 (97.7%)	4213 (70.9%)	1019014 (97.5%)	
Yes	25931 (2.5%)	1912 (28.0%)	27843 (2.7%)		25315 (2.5%)	1853 (29.1%)	27168 (2.7%)		24359 (2.3%)	1731 (29.1%)	26090 (2.5%)	
OPTIME				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹
N	1018620	6839	1025459		1010560	6366	1016926		1039027	5942	1044969	
Mean (SD)	109.6 (90.7)	178.7 (137.6)	110.1 (91.3)		110.8 (91.0)	176.7 (139.3)	111.2 (91.6)		111.1 (91.1)	185.8 (141.2)	111.6 (91.6)	
Median (IQR)	84.0 (51.0,	137.0 (79.0,	85.0 (51.0,		85.0 (51.0,	135.0 (76.0,	85.0 (52.0,		85.0 (52.0,	144.0 (83.0,	86.0 (52.0,	
Range	0.0, 1434.0	0.0, 1166.0	0.0, 1434.0		0.0, 1440.0	2.0, 1357.0	0.0, 1440.0		0.0, 1440.0	0.0, 1107.0	0.0, 1440.0	

Abbreviations: ANESTHES = anesthesia type, ELECTSURG = elective surgery, IV = intravenous, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, NOTHBLEED = number of bleeding transfusions occurrences, OPTIME = operation time, OTHBLEED = occurrence of bleeding transfusions, RETURNOR = return to OR, and SURGSPEC = surgical specialty

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

Table 3
Study Characteristics by Surgical Specialties

	Cardiac REINTUB				Thoracic REINTUB				Neurosurgery REINTUB				ENT REINTUB			
	N (N=11909)	Y (N=382)	Total (N=12291)	P-value	N (N=35877)	Y (N=1028)	Total (N=36905)	P-value	N (N=163516)	Y (N=1611)	Total (N=165127)	P-value	N (N=78635)	Y (N=284)	Total (N=78919)	P-value
ANESTHES, n (%)				0.1311 ²				0.9745 ¹				0.5266 ²				0.0002 ²
Epidural	3 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (0.0%)		76 (0.2%)	3 (0.3%)	79 (0.2%)		29 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	29 (0.0%)		9 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (0.0%)	
General	11539 (96.9%)	380 (99.5%)	11919 (97.0%)		35643 (99.3%)	1020 (99.2%)	36663 (99.3%)		161225 (98.6%)	1596 (99.1%)	162821 (98.6%)		77603 (98.7%)	279 (98.2%)	77882 (98.7%)	
Local	7 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (0.1%)		9 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (0.0%)		97 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	97 (0.1%)		62 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	62 (0.1%)	
MAC/IV Sedation	304 (2.6%)	2 (0.5%)	306 (2.5%)		116 (0.3%)	4 (0.4%)	120 (0.3%)		1784 (1.1%)	14 (0.9%)	1798 (1.1%)		894 (1.1%)	4 (1.4%)	898 (1.1%)	
Regional	5 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (0.0%)		4 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (0.0%)		134 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	134 (0.1%)		10 (0.0%)	1 (0.4%)	11 (0.0%)	
Spinal	51 (0.4%)	0 (0.0%)	51 (0.4%)		29 (0.1%)	1 (0.1%)	30 (0.1%)		247 (0.2%)	1 (0.1%)	248 (0.2%)		57 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	57 (0.1%)	
ELECTSURG, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	5187 (43.6%)	214 (56.0%)	5401 (43.9%)		5107 (14.2%)	274 (26.7%)	5381 (14.6%)		29538 (18.1%)	956 (59.3%)	30494 (18.5%)		2868 (3.6%)	39 (13.7%)	2907 (3.7%)	
Unknown	7 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (0.1%)		21 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	21 (0.1%)		50 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	50 (0.0%)		149 (0.2%)	1 (0.4%)	150 (0.2%)	
Yes	6715 (56.4%)	168 (44.0%)	6883 (56.0%)		30749 (85.7%)	754 (73.3%)	31503 (85.4%)		133928 (81.9%)	655 (40.7%)	134583 (81.5%)		75618 (96.2%)	244 (85.9%)	75862 (96.1%)	
EMERGENCY, n (%)				0.0023 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	10909 (91.6%)	333 (87.2%)	11242 (91.5%)		34891 (97.3%)	978 (95.1%)	35869 (97.2%)		156066 (95.4%)	1201 (74.5%)	157267 (95.2%)		77781 (98.9%)	269 (94.7%)	78050 (98.9%)	
Yes	1000 (8.4%)	49 (12.8%)	1049 (8.5%)		986 (2.7%)	50 (4.9%)	1036 (2.8%)		7450 (4.6%)	410 (25.5%)	7860 (4.8%)		854 (1.1%)	15 (5.3%)	869 (1.1%)	
NOTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
0	6105 (51.3%)	102 (26.7%)	6207 (50.5%)		34094 (95.0%)	767 (74.6%)	34861 (94.5%)		156955 (96.0%)	1318 (81.8%)	158273 (95.8%)		77749 (98.9%)	233 (82.0%)	77982 (98.8%)	
1	5804 (48.7%)	280 (73.3%)	6084 (49.5%)		1783 (5.0%)	261 (25.4%)	2044 (5.5%)		6561 (4.0%)	293 (18.2%)	6854 (4.2%)		886 (1.1%)	51 (18.0%)	937 (1.2%)	
OTHBLEED, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	3869 (32.5%)	61 (16.0%)	3930 (32.0%)		34094 (95.0%)	767 (74.6%)	34861 (94.5%)		156955 (96.0%)	1318 (81.8%)	158273 (95.8%)		77749 (98.9%)	233 (82.0%)	77982 (98.8%)	
No Complication	2236 (18.8%)	41 (10.7%)	2277 (18.5%)													
Transfusions/Intraop/Postop	5804 (48.7%)	280 (73.3%)	6084 (49.5%)		1783 (5.0%)	261 (25.4%)	2044 (5.5%)		6561 (4.0%)	293 (18.2%)	6854 (4.2%)		886 (1.1%)	51 (18.0%)	937 (1.2%)	
RETURNOR, n (%)				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²				<.0001 ²
No	11251 (94.5%)	263 (68.8%)	11514 (93.7%)		34446 (96.0%)	702 (68.3%)	35148 (95.2%)		158189 (96.7%)	1077 (66.9%)	159266 (96.5%)		76533 (97.3%)	165 (58.1%)	76698 (97.2%)	
Yes	658 (5.5%)	119 (31.2%)	777 (6.3%)		1431 (4.0%)	326 (31.7%)	1757 (4.8%)		5327 (3.3%)	534 (33.1%)	5861 (3.5%)		2102 (2.7%)	119 (41.9%)	2221 (2.8%)	
OPTIME				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹				<.0001 ¹
N	11905	382	12287		35875	1028	36903		163503	1611	165114		78630	283	78913	
Mean (SD)	233.7 (109.3)	278.2 (116.4)	235.1 (109.8)		151.1 (107.3)	238.4 (161.8)	153.5 (110.1)		156.1 (104.5)	212.2 (142.7)	156.6 (105.0)		120.5 (130.1)	292.4 (241.6)	121.1 (131.0)	
Median (IQR)	227.0 (165.0, 293.0)	269.0 (212.0, 334.0)	229.0 (166.0, 294.0)		126.0 (73.0, 198.0)	203.0 (110.0, 334.5)	127.0 (73.0, 201.0)		129.0 (84.0, 199.0)	173.0 (110.0, 273.0)	130.0 (84.0, 200.0)		84.0 (39.0, 149.0)	217.0 (105.0, 451.0)	84.0 (39.0, 150.0)	
Range	2.0, 1214.0	25.0, 694.0	2.0, 1214.0		0.0, 1144.0	9.0, 972.0	0.0, 1144.0		0.0, 1300.0	10.0, 894.0	0.0, 1300.0		0.0, 1440.0	6.0, 1357.0	0.0, 1440.0	

Abbreviations: ANESTHES = anesthesia type, ELECTSURG = elective surgery, IV = intravenous, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, NOTHBLEED = number of bleeding transfusions occurrences, OPTIME = operation time, OTHBLEED = occurrence of bleeding transfusions, RETURNOR = return to OR, and SURGSPEC = surgical specialty

¹ Kruskal-Wallis p-value

² Chi-Square p-value

Fig. 1. Multivariate logistic regression modeling surgical factors from 2017 to 2019. Abbreviations = ANESTHES = anesthesia type, CI = confidence interval, ELECTSURG = elective surgery, IV = intravenous, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, OPTIME = operation time, OTHBLEED = occurrence of bleeding transfusions, and RETURNOR = return to OR

¹ Covariate Wald p-value

² Type 3 Wald p-value

Fig. 2. Multivariate logistic regression modeling surgical specialties.

Abbreviations: ANESTHES = anesthesia type, CI = confidence interval, ELECTSURG = elective surgery, IV = intravenous, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, OPTIME = operation time, OTHBLEED = occurrence of bleeding transfusions, and RETURNOR = return to OR

¹ Covariate Wald p-value

4. Discussion

A multitude of variables produced statistically significant results within the dataset and each of these bear meaningful considerations for perioperative anesthetic management of surgical patients. The average incidence rate of UIs between 2017 to 2019 was found to be 0.62% (Table 2), which was lower than the incidence rate seen in the existing literature on the topic (3%) [5]. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that this data is more recent and taken from a global dataset. In comparison, previous literature takes into account both surgical factors and patient-related factors that contribute to UI, may come from institutions with varied surgical practices and include a range of specific surgical populations. However, the lower incidence rate of 0.62% could also indicate that newer data from 2017 to 2019 more accurately depicts the prevalence of pre-Covid UI, alluding to better surgical practices and decreasing UIs overall. Clinically, patients can be screened in advance by both the surgical and anesthesia teams in order to prepare for surgery. Preoperative labs can be drawn, diagnostic studies such as chest x-ray and echocardiograms can be performed to assess patient cardiopulmonary status and function. Optimizing patients before high-risk surgical procedures allows both surgical and anesthesia teams to plan for the safest approach which maximizes patient safety, seen by the low incidences of UIs.

While the incidence rate for UIs (0.62%) was lower than some literature, this study found significant associations between multiple ACS-NSQIP variables and UIs. The most consistently noted variables that showed positive correlations with UI were bleeding occurrences within 72 hours of surgery start time (OTHBLEED), returns to operating room (RETURNOR), and total operative time (OPTIME). These variables were reliably associated with UIs when analyzed independent of surgical procedure, as well as within the context of the surgical specialties of interest in this study (cardiac, thoracic, neurosurgery, ENT). Elective versus emergent cases were also correlated with UIs when examined overall but not found to be consistently significant among every surgical specialties; it was noted that elective neuro and thoracic surgeries did exhibit negative correlations to UIs. Finally, one of the more interesting relationships uncovered in the data was the negative correlation between MAC/IV Sedation and Spinal anesthesia within the ANESTHES category.

4.1 Principle Anesthetic Technique

Discerning the most appropriate anesthetic approach for a given procedure is one of the most critical aspects of perioperative anesthetic case management. The “MAC/IV Sedation” category resulted in significantly decreased odds of exposure to UI during the perioperative period when compared to general anesthesia. When utilizing “MAC/IV Sedation” as the primary anesthetic approach, there was 38-55% decreased odds of experiencing an UI compared to patients who underwent general anesthesia. This is noteworthy as previous literature suggests that MAC cases that were unexpectedly converted to general anesthesia have been a contributing factor for intraoperative UI. Similarly, the “Spinal” anesthesia category of ACS-NSQIP cases was associated with 66-72% decreased odds of an UI during the years 2017 to 2019. These findings are novel because previous literature that investigated these anesthetic techniques was limited in terms of intraoperative contributors to UIs, and some literature suggested that any non-intubated patient is at risk for intraoperative UI [7]. From an anesthesia standpoint, this begs the question of whether non-intubated patients (i.e., in cases where the primary anesthetic technique

is MAC or spinal anesthesia) have a higher or lower risk of UI during the intraoperative period. If MAC and spinal anesthesia cases are not being converted to general endotracheal anesthesia, as indicated in this UI data (Table 2), then the intraoperative period may not be of primary concern when studying UIs. The current data demonstrates that spinal anesthesia and MAC anesthesia were associated with a lower incidence of UI but causation for the decrease in UI incidence was not determined. The implications of this finding (from an anesthesia perspective) now asks future research to determine where and when UIs are occurring. The findings of the study may help to focus resources and attention around the postoperative setting when assessing for and preventing UIs. However, further research will be necessary to better understand this relationship.

4.2 Total Operative Time

Operative time was a recurring variable seen in almost all surgical specialties and across all three years of investigation. On average, cases that resulted in an UI were about an hour longer than cases that did not result in an UI, when assessing the aggregate data between 2017 to 2019. Although the odds ratios for these categories did not show a strong relationship (Fig. 1-2), the mean operative times as listed in Table 2 show a large discrepancy between cases that did and did not result in UI. With the exception of ENT surgery, operative time showed a very strong and positive correlation with UI amongst the surgical specialties of interest. From an anesthesia perspective, providers need to be cognizant of the scheduled procedure and the anticipated length of time the case is booked for. If unexpected events occur during a case that prolong the operative time, anesthesia providers must anticipate the needs of the patient from a respiratory standpoint. Extubation readiness and postoperative planning are paramount for all surgical cases, but especially for those with unexpectedly long operative times.

4.3 Return to OR

The RETURNOR category showed the strongest correlation with UI when compared to all other variables of interest portrayed in Figures 1-2. The ORs across all three years and all four surgical specialties demonstrated an undeniable association between surgical cases that required a return to the operating room and UI. The RETURNOR group showed a 4-fold increase in odds of UI. This could be related to patient comorbidities and surgical acuity. Previous literature from the ACS-NSQIP database has shown that surgical acuity, patient comorbidities, surgical approach, and surgical specialty are significant risk factors for surgical cases requiring an unscheduled return to the operating room (uROR) [8]. This phenomenon has been relatively well studied and the need to return to the operating room following a surgical procedure is often indicative of a serious clinical condition [8]. The strong relationship between RETURNOR and UI seen in this study could be related to previously identified ACS-NSQIP data on unplanned return to the operating room (uROR). For example, risk factors such as patient comorbidities and surgical acuity (outlined in previous literature) [3] could potentially influence UIs in the RETURNOR patient population, as many of the surgical specialties examined in this study (cardiac, neurosurgery, thoracic) were commonly associated with multiple patient comorbidities. However, further research must be conducted to discern any potential relationships.

4.4 *Bleeding Occurrences and Transfusions*

Perioperative blood loss is of immense concern to the anesthesia provider. Prompt response to acute bleeding events is vital to patient resuscitation, and this data showed that blood loss can also lead to perioperative UI. Of all the cases that resulted in UI between 2017 to 2019, roughly one third of them were associated with a significant bleeding occurrence and blood transfusion. The multivariate analysis indicates an increased odds of UI for patients who received perioperative blood transfusions. Patients who received perioperative blood transfusions were at 80-94% increased odds of UI, demonstrating the strong association between bleeding occurrences and respiratory compromise as a result of hypoperfusion and hypoxia. While transfusing blood increases the oxygen-carrying capacity of blood, thus improving oxygenation of the body, there can also be potentially fatal reactions to blood transfusion such as Transfusion-Associated Circulatory Overload (TACO) or Transfusion-Related Acute Lung Injury (TRALI). TACO is a transfusion reaction that results in pulmonary edema and respiratory distress due to volume or circulatory overload which can worsen with patients who have other comorbidities such as congestive heart failure (CHF) [6]. TRALI is a syndrome that results from noncardiogenic pulmonary edema and potentially acute lung distress syndrome (ARDS) causing hypoxia from blood transfusion [6]. Both of these pathologies require immediate airway support and management to improve oxygenation, which can result in UIs. The life-threatening complications of bleeding occurrences and transfusions further emphasize the importance to continue the investigation between surgical factors and UIs. Anesthesia providers must be astute and timely with their response to acute perioperative blood loss and understand that this may put the patient at increased risk for respiratory compromise.

4.5 *Emergent and Elective Cases*

Cases confirmed as elective procedures (ELECTSURG) showed a decrease in odds of UI by 24-26%. This negative correlation suggests that elective procedures are less likely to result in perioperative airway compromise. From an anesthesia perspective, this seems plausible as patients who come for elective procedures are most likely medically optimized and the necessary case planning is implemented.

4.6 *Surgical Specialties*

4.6.1 *Bleeding Occurrences and Transfusions*

The surgical specialties data showed many similarities between all four surgical disciplines (cardiac, thoracic, neurosurgery, ENT). OTHBLEED was seen throughout the data set as a strong indicator of increased odds of UI. This relationship was evident when examined independent of surgical procedure as well as throughout individual surgical specialties. It was most prominently seen in the cardiac surgery and ENT surgery patient populations. Bleeding that required blood transfusions showed almost a 75% incidence rate amongst cardiac surgery patients who experienced UI. ENT cases requiring blood transfusions exhibited 155% increase in odds of UI (Table 3). Highly vascular structures associated with ENT surgery such as the tonsils and thyroid, in combination with a shared airway, should put anesthesia providers on high alert for perioperative respiratory compromise and possibly UI. In addition, the data shows approximately 50% increased odds of UI for neurosurgery cases that experienced bleeding

events. Lastly, thoracic surgery cases where bleeding events transpired were at 100% increased odds of undergoing UI. However, the number of transfusions that cause this association with UI still needs to be investigated. Ultimately, any incidence of blood transfusion should put anesthesia providers on high alert regarding postoperative patient planning in order to avoid UI.

4.6.2 Operative Time

For anesthesia providers it is necessary to consider the length of surgery and understand the potential for perioperative UI if the duration of the procedure is longer than anticipated. Across all four surgical specialties, longer than anticipated OPTIME was positively correlated with UIs. For example, thoracic surgeries that resulted in UI were about one and a half hours longer than thoracic surgeries that did not result in an UI. From an anesthesia perspective, lengthy operative times are often associated with intraoperative complications, thus anesthesia providers should therefore consider the potential of UI in their postoperative planning. As expected, RETURNOR showed a dramatic increase in the odds of UI.

4.6.3 Return to OR

A profound relationship was found between ENT surgery cases that required a return visit to the operating room and UI (OR [95% CI] = 8.773 [6.436-11.959]) (Fig. 2). When ENT surgery patients experienced a return to the OR the odds of UI increased by approximately 775%. Cardiac surgery cases that required a return visit to the OR carried approximately six-fold increased odds of requiring a UI (Fig. 2). Additionally, neurosurgery cases that required a return trip to the operating room were at roughly 600% increased odds of UI (Fig. 2). The data illustrated approximately 475% increased odds of UI within the thoracic surgery group (Fig. 2). From a practical standpoint, anesthesia providers can expect that any surgical patient requiring a return to the OR will most often require reintubation if a secured airway is not already present.

4.6.4 Emergent and Elective Cases

Interestingly, ELECTSURG showed a negative correlation with UIs for neurosurgery and thoracic surgery patients. The elective neurosurgery cases, referred to as ELECTSURG showed a decreased odds of UI (OR [95% CI] = 0.536 [0.466-0.617]) (Fig. 2). Patients coming for elective neurosurgery experienced a 46% decrease in odds of UI. Elective thoracic surgery cases had 38% reduced odds of UI. The data suggests elective procedures may be at a reduced risk of UI which seems reasonable when comparing elective procedures with urgent or emergent cases. From a clinical standpoint, elective procedures facilitate advanced preoperative planning that allow for patient optimization before surgery. This could include preoperative transfusions to minimize effects of anemia, especially for high-risk surgical specialties mentioned in this scholarly project. Moreover, with optimization, the surgeons can better plan the surgical approach to decrease operative time. This may help explain the reduction in UIs seen in elective procedures. Overall, the surgical specialties data elicits convincing, consistent results that impact perioperative planning and anesthetic case management. Future studies should examine other surgical specialties and

4.7 Limitations

The results of this study show compelling relationships between multiple surgical variables and UIs. However, they should be understood within the context of the limitations of

secondary data analysis. The ACS-NSQIP database only collects data from hospitals participating with ACS-NSQIP and is not representative of every hospital or patient population [9]. Moreover, data from ACS-NSQIP does not thoroughly distinguish between the severity of comorbidities, indications for surgery, or procedural outcomes [10]. Other potential confounding variables include surgeon technique/skill level, preexisting airway disease, or postoperative disposition (ambulatory, inpatient, etc.) [9]. Of note, the years 2017 to 2019 were intentionally chosen as to satisfy a recent secondary data analysis while also excluding data from the recent COVID-19 pandemic. Any data beyond 2019 may have introduced additional bias into the study as fewer elective surgeries were performed during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, the prevalence of a worldwide respiratory virus could have skewed UI data even further. Nonetheless, the large sample size and complete datasets allowed a sufficient cross-sectional analysis of surgical factors affecting UIs.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrated that UIs happen rarely (0.62%) but when considering the disastrous complications of this negative phenomenon, more can be done to identify and anticipate the needs of patients at risk of UI. Surgical factors that were found to have strong associations with UIs included operative time, return to OR, and perioperative bleeding. Patients receiving MAC/IV sedation or spinal anesthesia may be at a lower risk of UI, as are elective thoracic and neurosurgery patients. Further research is necessary to better understand these relationships. Performing more comprehensive literature reviews, expanding secondary data analysis, and developing interventions such as clinical support tools (risk indices) could help identify and appropriately plan for patients at increased risk of UI.

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